

**TOPOLOGICAL DATA ANALYSIS IN ANALYZING
THE SIMILARITY OF AIR POLLUTANTS'
BEHAVIOR ACROSS AIR QUALITY MONITORING
STATIONS IN MALAYSIA**

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BEHAVIOR ACROSS AIR QUALITY MONITORING
STATIONS IN MALAYSIA**

by

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	ii
TABLE OF CONTENTS	iii
LIST OF TABLES	vii
LIST OF FIGURES	viii
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	xiii
LIST OF SYMBOLS	xv
LIST OF APPENDICES	xvi
ABSTRAK	xvii
ABSTRACT	xix
CHAPTER 1 INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 Research Background	1
1.2 Topological Data Analysis (TDA).....	3
1.3 Problem Statements	5
1.4 Research Questions.....	6
1.5 Research Objectives.....	6
1.6 Scope of Study	7
1.7 Significance of Study	8
1.8 Thesis Outline	8
CHAPTER 2 LITERATURE REVIEW	10
2.1 Introduction.....	10
2.2 Traditional HACA in Analysing Air Quality Data.....	10
2.3 Topological Data Analysis (TDA) in Environmental Studies	12
2.3.1 Conventional Mapper (CM).....	14

2.3.2	Ball Mapper (BM).....	16
2.4	Motivation of Study.....	17
CHAPTER 3	METHODOLOGY	18
3.1	Introduction.....	18
3.2	Datasets.....	19
3.3	Topological Data Analysis (TDA).....	22
3.3.1	Conventional Mapper (CM) Algorithm	23
3.3.1(a)	The Nerve Theorem.....	24
3.3.1(b)	Reeb Graph	25
3.3.1(c)	The Topological Version of CM	26
3.3.1(d)	The Statistical Version of CM.....	27
3.3.4	Ball Mapper (BM) Algorithm	32
3.3.5	Graph Invariant	36
3.3.5(a)	Estrada Index.....	37
3.3.5(b)	Graph Density	39
3.3.5(c)	Number of Cycle Basis	40
3.3.5(d)	Fragmentation Index.....	41
3.3.5(e)	Node Degree Distribution of Topological Graphs	41
3.4	Summary.....	43
CHAPTER 4	TOPOLOGICAL GRAPH REPRESENTATION OF AIR POLLUTANTS' BEHAVIOR USING CONVENTIONAL MAPPER AND BALL MAPPER ALGORITHMS.....	44
4.1	Introduction.....	44
4.2	Simulation.....	45
4.2.1	Implementation of the CM Algorithm on the Simulated Dataset	47
4.2.2	Implementation of the BM Algorithm on the Simulated Dataset	49

4.3	PM ₁₀ Dataset for 2012 to 2015 and 2018 to 2020	53
4.3.1	CM Topological Graph for 2012 PM ₁₀	54
4.3.2	CM Topological Graph for 2013 PM ₁₀	60
4.3.3	CM Topological Graph for 2014 PM ₁₀	64
4.3.4	CM Topological Graph for 2015 PM ₁₀	67
4.3.5	CM Topological Graph for 2018 PM ₁₀	70
4.3.6	CM Topological Graph for 2019 PM ₁₀	72
4.3.7	CM Topological Graph for 2020 PM ₁₀	75
4.3.8	Node Degree Distribution of Yearly PM ₁₀ Topological Graphs.....	77
4.3.9	Comparison between Quantitative and Qualitative Analysis of PM ₁₀ Behavior	78
4.4	Comparative Analysis of CM and BM in Analyzing CO, NO ₂ , PM _{2.5} , PM ₁₀ , O ₃ , and SO ₂ Datasets for 2018 to 2020	80
4.4.1	CM and BM Topological Graphs of NO ₂	82
	4.4.1(a) Comparison between CM and BM for NO ₂	84
4.4.2	CM and BM Topological Graph of PM ₁₀	87
	4.4.2(a) Comparison between BM and CM of PM ₁₀	89
4.4.3	CM and BM Topological Graphs of PM _{2.5}	91
4.4.4	CM and BM Topological Graph of CO	93
4.4.5	CM and BM Topological Graph of O ₃	95
4.4.6	CM and BM Topological Graph of SO ₂	97
4.5	Quantitative Analysis of CM and BM Topological Graphs for NO ₂ , PM ₁₀ , PM _{2.5} , O ₃ , CO, and SO ₂ Using Graph invariants	98
4.6	Comparison between TDA techniques and traditional HACA in Analyzing Air Pollutants Behavior.....	101
4.7	Summary.....	102
CHAPTER 5 DISCUSSION		104

5.1	Introduction.....	104
5.2	Discussion of Results.....	104
5.3	Significance of Quantitative Analysis of CM and BM Topological Graphs Using Graph Invariants	108
5.4	Advantages of Topological Clustering for Pollution Analysis and Control.....	109
5.5	Study Limitations.....	111
CHAPTER 6 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK		112
6.1	Conclusion	112
6.2	Future Work.....	113
REFERENCES		114
APPENDICES		
LIST OF PUBLICATIONS		

LIST OF TABLES

		Page
Table 3.1	List of 60 air quality monitoring stations in Figure 3.2	20
Table 3.2	Air Pollution Index (API)	21
Table 3.3	Ambient Air Quality Guidelines (MAAQG) levels.....	21
Table 3.4	Illustration of adjacency Table of Figure 3.12.....	38
Table 3.5	Node degree of the topological graph in Figure 3.12	42
Table 4.1	The models used to simulate the stationary and non-stationary time series	45
Table 4.2	Descriptive statistics of PM ₁₀ daily average concentration for each year from 2012 to 2015 and 2018 to 2020.....	54
Table 4.3	Yearly comparisons of PM ₁₀ concentration mean differences with paired <i>t</i> -test.....	79
Table 4.4	Descriptive statistics of CO, NO ₂ , PM _{2.5} , PM ₁₀ , O ₃ , and SO ₂ for 2018 to 2020.....	81
Table 4.5	Advantages and Disadvantages of CM and BM Algorithms.....	100

LIST OF FIGURES

		Page
Figure 1.1	Overview of the topological data analysis Mapper process (Lum et al., 2013)	4
Figure 2.1	Datasaurus dozen (Gillespie et al., 2024)	13
Figure 2.2	Example of a topological graph	15
Figure 3.1	Research Methodology Flowchart	19
Figure 3.2	Location of 60 air quality monitoring stations across Malaysia.	20
Figure 3.3	Examples of simplices in different dimensions	23
Figure 3.4	Nerve construction from a point cloud and its associated simplicial complex	25
Figure 3.5	Reeb graph construction for a Torus using a height function.....	26
Figure 3.6	Conventional Mapper Flowchart	27
Figure 3.7	Flowchart of the PCA algorithm.....	29
Figure 3.8	HACA Flowchart	30
Figure 3.9	Toy P-shape point cloud used in illustrating CM algorithm implementation.	31
Figure 3.10	Ball Mapper Flowchart	32
Figure 3.11	Toy P-shape point cloud used in illustrating the BM algorithm implementation and its output.....	36
Figure 3.12	Toy topological graph G	38
Figure 3.13	Histogram of the node degree distribution of the topological graph in Figure 3.12	42
Figure 4.1	Example of a stationary simulated time series by AR (1)	46
Figure 4.2	Example of non-stationary simulated time series produced by ARIMA (1,1,1).....	46
Figure 4.3	Topological graph of simulated time series with 5 covers and 20% overlaps produced from the CM application	47

Figure 4.4	Plot of simulated time series clustered in Nodes S1, S2, S6, S9, and S10 of simulated CM topological graph.....	48
Figure 4.5	Topological graphs of simulated time series by varying the parameters. (a) 5-Covers, 5% overlap, and the number of clusters is 2 (b) 5 Covers, 30% overlap and the number of clusters is 2 (c) 5 Covers, 50% overlap and the number of clusters is 2 (d) 5 Covers, 80% overlap and the number of clusters is 2 (e) 2 Covers, 30% overlap and the number of clusters is 4 (f) 4 Covers, 30% overlap and the number of clusters is 4 (g) 5 Covers, 30% overlap and the number of clusters is 4 and (h) 10 Covers, 30% overlap and the number of clusters is 4.	49
Figure 4.6	Topological graph of simulated time series generated using the Ball Mapper (BM) algorithm.	50
Figure 4.7	Simulated time series clustered within Nodes 0, 125, 131, and 139 of the Ball Mapper (BM) topological graph in Figure 4.6 with $\varepsilon = 0.04$	51
Figure 4.8	BM topological graph of simulated time series with $\varepsilon = 0.003$ produced from the BM algorithm	52
Figure 4.9	BM topological graph of simulated time series with $\varepsilon = 0.001$ produced from the BM algorithm	52
Figure 4.10	Normalized Factor loading PC1 and partition of stations into 5 covers; Cover 0, 1, ..., 4, with 30% overlap for 2012 PM ₁₀	55
Figure 4.11	Graphical user interface displaying the topological graph generated using the Conventional Mapper (CM) algorithm through the KeplerMapper application.....	56
Figure 4.12	2012 PM ₁₀ CM topological graph with 5 Covers and 30% overlaps	57
Figure 4.13	Time series plots of 2012 PM ₁₀ for monitoring stations clustered in Nodes A5, A3, A9, and A16 of the Conventional Mapper (CM) topological graph	58
Figure 14	Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) heatmap that measures the similarity between the time series of air quality monitoring stations clustered in Nodes A5, A2, A9, and A16 of the 2012 PM ₁₀ Conventional Mapper (CM) topological graph	59
Figure 4.15	Geographical locations of air quality monitoring stations clustered in the most connected Nodes (A1 through A5) of the 2012 topological graph	60
Figure 4.16	2013 PM ₁₀ CM topological graph with 5 Covers and 30% overlaps	61

Figure 4.17	Time series plots of 2013 PM ₁₀ for monitoring stations clustered in Nodes B1, B2, B11, and B8 of the CM topological graph.....	62
Figure 4.18	DTW heatmap measuring the similarity between the time series of stations clustered in nodes B1, B2, B8, and B11 of the 2013 PM ₁₀ CM's topological graph	63
Figure 4.19	Geographical locations of air quality monitoring stations clustered in the most connected Nodes (B1 through B9) of the 2013 topological graph.....	64
Figure 4.20	2014 PM ₁₀ CM topological graph with 5 Covers and 30% overlaps	65
Figure 4.21	Time series plots of 2014 PM ₁₀ for monitoring stations clustered in Nodes C7, C3, C1, and C12 of CM topological graph	65
Figure 4.22	DTW heatmap measuring the similarity between the time series of stations clustered in Nodes C1, C3, C7, and C11 of the 2014 PM ₁₀ CM's topological graph.	66
Figure 4.23	Geographical locations of air quality monitoring stations clustered in the most connected Nodes C1 through C6 of the 2014 topological graph.	67
Figure 4.24	2015 PM ₁₀ CM topological graph with 5 Covers and 30% overlaps for	68
Figure 4.25	Time series plots of 2015 PM ₁₀ for monitoring stations clustered in Nodes D1, D4, D7, and D15 of CM topological graph.....	68
Figure 4.26	DTW heatmap measuring the similarity between the time series of stations clustered in nodes D1, D4, D7, and D15 of the 2015 PM ₁₀ CM topological graph.	69
Figure 4.27	Geographical locations of air quality monitoring stations clustered in the most connected Nodes D1 through D12 of the 2015 topological graph.....	70
Figure 4.28	2018 PM ₁₀ CM topological graph with 5 Covers and 30% overlaps for	71
Figure 4.29	Time series plots of 2018 PM ₁₀ for monitoring stations clustered in Nodes E4, E11, E8, and E13 of the topological graph.....	71
Figure 4.30	Geographical locations of air quality monitoring stations clustered in the most connected Nodes E1 through E4 of the 2018 topological graph.....	72
Figure 4.31	2019 PM ₁₀ CM topological graph with 5 Covers and 30% overlaps	73
Figure 4.32	Time series of stations clustered in Nodes F7, F3, F1, and F16 of 2019 PM ₁₀ CM topological graph	73

Figure 4.33	DTW heatmap measuring the similarity between the time series of stations clustered in nodes F1, F2, and F3 of the 2019 PM ₁₀ CM topological graph.	74
Figure 4.34	Geographical locations of air quality monitoring stations clustered in the most connected Nodes F6 through F8 of the 2019 topological graph	74
Figure 4.35	2020 PM ₁₀ CM topological graph with 5 Covers and 30% overlaps for	76
Figure 4.36	Time series of stations clustered in Nodes G6, G4, G1, and G12 of 2020 PM ₁₀ CM topological graph.....	76
Figure 4.37	Geographical locations of air quality monitoring stations clustered in the most connected Nodes G1 through G10 of the 2020 topological graph.....	77
Figure 4.38	Node degree distribution of 2012, 2013, 2014, 2015, 2018, 2019, and 2020 PM ₁₀ topological graphs	78
Figure 4.39	Spearman correlation heatmap showing the relationships between annual PM ₁₀ concentrations across all monitoring stations from 2012 to 2020	80
Figure 4.40	NO ₂ CM topological graph with 7 Covers, 30% overlaps and 20 nodes	83
Figure 4.41	NO ₂ BM topological graph with $\varepsilon = 0.078$ and 20 nodes	84
Figure 4.42	Time series of stations clustered in: (a) Node 12 of the CM graph, and (b) Node A1 of the BM graph	85
Figure 4.43	DTW heatmap measuring the similarities in the time series of randomly selected stations clustered in nodes of the CM and BM topological graph of NO ₂	86
Figure 4.44	Histogram comparing node degree distribution of BM with CM topological graphs of NO ₂	87
Figure 4.45	PM ₁₀ CM topological graph with 4 Covers, 30% overlap, and 16 nodes	88
Figure 4.46	PM ₁₀ BM topological graph with $\varepsilon = 0.062$ and 16 nodes.....	89
Figure 4.47	Time series of the stations clustered in (a) Node B1 of the CM topological graph and (b) Node 36 of the BM's topological graph.....	90
Figure 4.48	(a) DTW heatmap measuring the similarities in the time series of randomly selected stations clustered in Nodes N1, N5, and Node 36, 14 of the CM and BM topological graphs of PM ₁₀ , respectively. (b) Histogram comparing node degree distribution of CM with BM topological graphs.	91

Figure 4.49	PM _{2.5} CM topological graph with 5 Covers, 20% overlap, and 20 nodes ...	92
Figure 4.50	PM _{2.5} BM topological graph with $\varepsilon = 0.065$ and 19 nodes	92
Figure 4.51	Time series of the stations (a) clustered in Node H2 of the CM topological graph (b) clustered in Node 20 of the BM topological graph (c) Histogram comparing node degree distribution of BM with CM topological graphs ...	93
Figure 4.52	CO CM topological graph with 7 Covers and 40% overlap and 20 nodes ..	93
Figure 4.53	CO BM topological graph with $\varepsilon = 0.048$ and 20 nodes	94
Figure 4.54	Time series of the stations clustered in (a) Node M7 of the CM topological graph (b) Node 1 of the BM topological graph (c) Histogram comparing node degree distribution of BM with CM graphs of CO	94
Figure 4.55	O ₃ CM topological graph with 5 Covers and 40% overlap and 20 nodes ...	95
Figure 4.56	O ₃ BM topological graph with $\varepsilon = 0.06$ and 22 nodes	96
Figure 4.57	Time series of the stations clustered in (a) Node G1 of the CM topological graph (b) Node 2 of the BM topological graph (c) Histogram comparing node degree distribution of BM with CM	96
Figure 4.58	SO ₂ CM topological graph with 7 Covers and 45% overlap, and 23 nodes	97
Figure 4.59	SO ₂ BM topological graph with $\varepsilon = 0.014$ and 22 nodes	98
Figure 4.60	Time series of the stations clustered in (a) Node L7 of the CM topological graph (b) Node 37 of the BM topological graph (c) Histogram comparing node degree distribution of BM with CM graphs of SO ₂	98
Figure 4.61	Graphs of the (a) density of BM and CM topological graphs (b) Estrada index (EE) of BM and CM topological graphs (c) Fragmentation index (FI) of BM and CM topological graphs (d) the number of cycle basis of BM and CM topological graphs	100
Figure 4.62	NO ₂ Dendrogram produced by traditional HACA	102

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

TDA	Topological Data Analysis
CM	Conventional Mapper
BM	Ball Mapper
HACA	Hierarchical Agglomerative Clustering Algorithm
DBSCAN	Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise
DTW	Dynamic Time Warping
DOE	Department of Environment
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
UMAP	Uniform Manifold Approximation Projection
t-SNE	t-Distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding
O ₃	Ozone
CO	Carbon monoxide
NO ₂	Nitrogen dioxide
SO ₂	Sulfur dioxide
PM ₁₀	Particulate Matter less than 10 microns
PM _{2.5}	Particulate Matter less than 2.5 microns
AQI	Air Quality Index
API	Air Pollution Index
MAAQG	Malaysian Ambient Air Quality Guidelines
WHO	World Health Organization
MCO	Movement Control Order
AR	Autoregressive
MA	Moving Average

ARMA	Autoregressive Moving Average
ARIMA	Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average
EE	Estrada Index
FI	Fragmentation Index
CC	Connected Components

LIST OF SYMBOLS

τ	Topology
X	Set
f	Continuous function
U	Open set or subset
α	Indexing set
\mathcal{U}	Cover or collection of open sets
$N(\mathcal{U})$	Nerve Complex
σ	Simplex
C_i	Cluster
$G(N, E)$	Topological graph G
N	Nodes of a topological graph
E	Edge of a topological graph
$B_\varepsilon(c_i)$	Ball centered at c_i
ε	Radius of ball
β_0	0 th Betti number
β_1	1 st Betti number
$\delta(n)$	Adjacency number
k	Node degree
$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$	micrograms per cubic meter
ppm	Part Per Million

LIST OF APPENDICES

APPENDIX A

TABLE OF STATIONS CLUSTERED IN THE NODES OF
THE CM TOPOLOGICAL GRAPHS

**ANALISIS DATA BERTOPOLOGI DALAM MENGANALISIS KESERUPAAN
KELAKUAN PENCEMAR UDARA ANTARA STESEN-STESEN PENGAWASAN
KUALITI UDARA DI MALAYSIA**

ABSTRAK

Pencemaran udara kini menjadi salah satu cabaran global utama yang berpunca daripada aktiviti perindustrian, pembinaan, pelepasan kenderaan dan pelbagai aktiviti manusia yang lain. Kajian ini menyelidik tingkah laku pencemar udara melalui pendekatan kualitatif dengan menggunakan teknik Analisis Data Bertopologi (ADB), iaitu Mapper konvensional (MK) dan variannya, Mapper Bebola (MB). Kaedah tersebut digunakan untuk menganalisis enam bahan pencemar udara utama (NO_2 , PM_{10} , $\text{PM}_{2.5}$, O_3 , CO , dan SO_2) yang diambil dari 60 stesen pemantauan kualiti udara di seluruh Malaysia. Graf topologi yang dibina menggunakan algoritma MK mendedahkan kelompok kawasan dan stesen yang menunjukkan tingkah laku pencemar yang serupa. Hasil kajian menunjukkan persamaan dalam tingkah laku PM_{10} pada tahun 2013, 2015, dan 2020. Pendekatan ini berpotensi untuk menunjukkan visualisasi kelompok yang lebih jelas dan berintuitif, serta mencerminkan hubungan geografi berbanding kaedah pengelompokan kuantitatif tradisional seperti analisis kelompok aglomeratif berhierarki (AKAB). Struktur graf topologi ini turut dianalisis menggunakan metrik graf bagi membandingkan keberkesanan MK dan MB dalam menangkap corak pencemaran udara secara setempat dan menyeluruh. Walaupun kedua-dua kaedah ini memberikan maklumat yang bermakna dan visualisasi tingkah laku pencemar yang lebih baik, algoritma MB memberikan perwakilan yang lebih berkesan pada tingkah laku bahan pencemar gas yang kompleks. Dapatan ini terbukti melalui ketumpatan graf yang tinggi bagi graf topologi MB dengan masing-masing NO_2 , O_3 , CO , dan SO_2 menunjukkan nilai 15%, 10%, 32% dan 25%, manakala graf topologi MK menghasilkan ketumpatan yang rendah, masing-masing menunjukkan 4%, 5%, 6% dan 5% untuk bahan-bahan pencemar tersebut. Secara keseluruhannya, hasil kajian ini

mencadangkan pendekatan ini sebagai kaedah alternatif bagi mengenal pasti homogeniti antara stesen-stesen pengawasan kualiti udara dan seterusnya menyumbang kepada pengoptimuman pengawasan dan pengurusan kualiti udara.

**TOPOLOGICAL DATA ANALYSIS IN ANALYZING THE SIMILARITY OF AIR
POLLUTANTS' BEHAVIOR ACROSS AIR QUALITY MONITORING STATIONS
IN MALAYSIA**

ABSTRACT

Air pollution is increasingly recognized as a major global issue resulting from industrial processes, urban development, transportation emissions, and a wide range of human activities. This study investigates air pollutant behavior through a qualitative approach, utilizing topological data analysis (TDA) techniques, the conventional Mapper (CM), and its variant Ball Mapper (BM). It analyzes six major air pollutants (NO_2 , PM_{10} , $\text{PM}_{2.5}$, O_3 , CO , and SO_2) collected from 60 air quality monitoring stations across Malaysia. The topological graphs generated using the CM algorithm revealed clusters of regions and stations exhibiting similar pollutant behavior. The results showed similar patterns in PM_{10} behavior across the years 2013, 2015, and 2020. This approach potentially offers a clearer and more intuitive visualization of cluster similarities, reflecting geographical relationships, compared to traditional quantitative clustering methods such as hierarchical agglomerative clustering analysis (HACA). The structure of the topological graphs is further examined using graph metrics to compare the effectiveness of the CM and BM algorithms in capturing local and global pollutant trends. While both methods provided valuable insights and better visualizations of pollutant behavior, the BM algorithm offered a more effective representation of the complex behavior of gaseous pollutants. This is evident in the higher graph densities of the BM topological graph for NO_2 , O_3 , CO , and SO_2 , which are 15%, 10%, 32%, and 25%, respectively. In comparison, the CM topological graph of the same pollutants yields lower densities of 4%, 5%, 6% and 5%, respectively. Overall, the findings suggest that this approach may serve as a viable alternative

for identifying homogeneity in air quality monitoring stations, potentially contributing to the optimization of air quality monitoring and management.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Research Background

Air pollution has become a significant global challenge in recent decades, primarily due to rapid urbanization and industrialization, particularly in developing nations (Shi et al., 2020; Wu and Chang, 2020). The rising levels of air pollution and the challenges in managing it effectively are significant concerns (Zeng et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2020). As a developing nation, Malaysia also contends with increasing air pollution issues, which pose significant risks to public health and the environment (Usmani et al., 2020; Chin et al., 2019). Addressing this issue requires implementing effective mitigation strategies and conducting comprehensive analyses to better understand pollutant behavior through air quality monitoring and data analysis (Sofia et al., 2020). Air quality monitoring is essential for mitigating and managing the effects of air pollution within any ecosystem (Gulia et al., 2020).

This environmental challenge stems from the release of harmful pollutants into the atmosphere, which harms both human health and the natural environment (WHO, 2024). Major pollutants affecting air quality include particulate matter (PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}), which can reduce visibility and penetrate deep into the lungs and bloodstream, causing respiratory and cardiovascular diseases (Areal et al., 2022; Maleki et al., 2022; Latif et al., 2018). Additionally, nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) and sulfur dioxide (SO₂) emissions, primarily from vehicle exhaust and industrial activities, contribute to the formation of acid rain and smog, thereby exacerbating air quality deterioration. Ground-level ozone (O₃), a secondary pollutant, exacerbates health issues such as asthma, while carbon monoxide (CO), primarily emitted from the combustion of fossil fuels, poses significant health risks (Peng et al., 2021). The accumulation of these pollutants harms human health, affects wildlife, damages vegetation, and contributes to climate change,

highlighting the need for more analytical tools to monitor and investigate pollutant behaviors across designated air quality monitoring stations.

Investigating the behavior of pollutants between air quality monitoring stations is essential for enhancing the efficiency of air quality management. In Malaysia, the Department of Environment (DOE) monitors and generates large amounts of data by recording the daily average concentrations of six major air pollutants: NO₂, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, O₃, CO, and SO₂ (DOE, 2024). However, the vast geographical area of Malaysia leads to varying air quality behavior, creating challenges in understanding spatial and temporal pollution trends for more accurate air quality forecasting and management (Naidin et al., 2024). Identifying regions with similar air pollution behaviors is crucial for accurately locating local emissions, reducing redundant air quality monitoring stations, and assisting decision makers and stakeholders in implementing effective pollution control measures to enhance air quality management (Stolz et al., 2020).

However, the volume of data generated from pollutant concentration measurements across numerous monitoring stations poses a substantial challenge for practical analysis. The complexity of the dataset requires advanced techniques to analyze and extract hidden information effectively. Traditional quantitative methods have proven helpful in this regard, each offering unique insights in the context of environmental monitoring. Time series analysis has been applied to monitor the trend of pollutants over time, enabling researchers to predict future trends of these pollutants (Yang et al., 2021). Descriptive statistics have been applied to summarize pollutant concentrations within specific areas, providing a clear overview of the dataset (Ibe et al., 2020). Also, correlation analysis reveals significant associations between pollutant concentration levels and their health impacts (Jalili et al., 2020). Regression analysis is used to predict pollutant concentrations based on various predictors, including weather conditions, traffic density, geographical location, seasonal variation, and industrial activities (Vasseur & Aznarte, 2021). In addition, hierarchical agglomerative clustering analysis

(HACA), k-means, and DBSCAN clustering methods classify areas based on similar air quality patterns (Govender & Sivakumar, 2020; Zhang and Yang, 2022; Suris et al., 2022). These methods identify distinct groups of stations with similar pollutant behavior and potential sources, such as industrial activities and high-traffic areas, enabling the development of targeted policies for effective pollution control (Zhao et al., 2016; Chen et al., 2015). This approach also provides valuable insights into the quantitative characteristics of pollutants. However, traditional clustering methods are often lacking in qualitative aspects and in uncovering hidden insights inherent in the datasets. As a result, there is a need for more analytical methods capable of extracting this hidden qualitative information and providing a simpler representation of the dataset, such as topological data analysis (TDA) techniques.

1.2 Topological Data Analysis (TDA)

TDA is an emerging field of mathematics that focuses on uncovering hidden patterns in high-dimensional datasets, offering qualitative insights into their structure and visualization (Chazal & Michel, 2021). TDA employs persistent homology and the Mapper algorithm to extract the underlying “shape” of data, emphasizing the idea that data has shape and shape has meaning (Todd & Petrov, 2022). This thesis focuses on the Mapper algorithm illustrated in Figure 1.1. Mapper applies a filter function to partition point cloud data into overlapping subsets or covers. Within each partition, similar data points are clustered, and connections are drawn between clusters that share common data points. The resulting graph, consisting of nodes and edges, captures the topological structure of the dataset by revealing patterns and relationships within the data. This graphical representation provides clearer and more interpretable visual insights into high-dimensional data.

Figure 1.1 Overview of the topological data analysis Mapper process (Lum et al., 2013)

This emerging field has demonstrated a wide range of applications across various disciplines. In biology, Campbell et al. (2019) employed the TDA Mapper for feature extraction in pain recognition based on physiological signals, addressing the problem of inconsistent feature selection in emotion recognition systems. In neurology, Caputi et al. (2021) utilized persistent homology to differentiate between normal and abnormal brain states. In the area of flood detection, Musa et al. (2021) and Ohanuba et al. (2021) proposed using persistent homology as a preprocessing technique to enhance the early detection of critical transitions, particularly flooding events in rivers. Ofori Boateng et al. (2021) applied persistent homology to compare aerosol optical depth (AOD) maps across different spatial resolutions without requiring regridding. Within the financial sector, Ismail et al. (2022) introduced a novel method for detecting early indicators of financial crises using persistent homology. Yang et al. (2024) applied the technique to improve the robustness of the Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LightGBM) algorithm in image classification tasks. These studies represent just a few of the many diverse applications of TDA across scientific and technological domains.

Although the TDA approach is increasingly applied across various fields, its potential remains underexplored in the study of air quality and pollution. A noteworthy study in this area

was conducted by Zulkepli et al. (2022), who utilized TDA, specifically persistent homology, to extract topological features from air quality datasets for categorizing days predominantly affected by haze episodes. Persistent homology is a technique within TDA that focuses on tracking the birth and death of topological features in a high-dimensional dataset (Malott et al., 2020; Corbet et al., 2019). A clustering algorithm is often integrated with the topological information provided by persistent homology to produce a better cluster (Otter et al., 2017). Persistent homology output is visualized through persistence diagrams or barcodes. In contrast, Mapper generates a topological graph that visually represents relationships between clusters through nodes and edges.

This thesis uses the Mapper algorithm and its variant Ball Mapper to analyze six major air pollutants in Malaysia, with the former regarded as the conventional approach. The conventional Mapper introduced by Singh et al. (2007) acts as a method for clustering and visualizing datasets based on their topological structure. It employs multiple parameters to generate a simplified representation of the dataset as a network structure, referred to as a topological graph. Ball Mapper simplifies the process of the conventional Mapper by using a single parameter. This parameter is the radius of a closed ball that covers all data points, consequently producing a topological graph. This approach could enable a comparative exploration of both algorithms in capturing and visualizing the underlying patterns and relationships within air quality datasets.

1.3 Problem Statements

Traditional clustering methods, such as hierarchical agglomerative clustering analysis (HACA), are commonly used to group air quality monitoring stations that exhibit similar pollutant behaviors. While these methods perform well in grouping data based on similarity, they are often limited in revealing topological relationships within the dataset. Additionally, the resulting clustering output can be complex to interpret, especially for high-dimensional

datasets. This challenge can be addressed using TDA techniques such as the conventional Mapper algorithm.

The conventional Mapper algorithm requires multiple parameters to be set up to construct a topological graph. In contrast, its variant, the Ball Mapper algorithm, relies on a single-parameter greedy algorithm to produce a topological graph. This reduced parameter dependency of the conventional Mapper algorithm can enhance the construction of topological graphs that reflect pollutant dynamics. Despite this potential, conventional Mapper and Ball Mapper algorithms have been underexplored in air quality studies.

Finally, a gap remains in comparative analysis between traditional quantitative clustering and qualitative TDA-based methods, such as the conventional Mapper and Ball Mapper, in terms of simplified visualization of air pollutant behavior. A comparative evaluation using graphs can help determine which method better captures pollutant behavior and provides clearer visual insights.

1.4 Research Questions

This thesis addresses the following research questions:

1. To what extent does the conventional Mapper algorithm capture similarities in pollutant behavior and reveal geographical relationships between air quality monitoring stations?
2. How effective is the Ball Mapper algorithm through a topological graph in representing complex air pollutant dynamics based on the data shape?
3. How do HACA, conventional Mapper, and Ball Mapper differ in visually representing clusters of monitoring stations according to pollutant behavior?

1.5 Research Objectives

To address the research questions, the thesis focused on the following key objectives :

1. To construct topological graphs using the conventional Mapper algorithm that elucidate yearly PM_{10} behavior and highlight the geographical relationships among air quality monitoring stations, based on topological structure.
2. To construct air pollutants topological graphs using the Ball Mapper algorithm and assess its effectiveness in capturing pollutant complex dynamics.
3. To compare the performance and visualization capabilities of traditional HACA, conventional Mapper, and Ball Mapper algorithms in clustering air quality monitoring stations based on pollutant behavior using graph invariants.

1.6 Scope of Study

This thesis examines the behavior of air pollutants across six regions in Malaysia using a qualitative approach. It focuses on pollutant concentration data collected from air quality monitoring stations between 2012-2015 and 2018-2020. To guide this investigation, the study is structured around three main objectives. The first objective investigates the behavior of PM_{10} using data from 52 air quality monitoring stations, analyzed through conventional Mapper topological graphs. The most connected components (subgraphs) are visualized on a map of Malaysia to show how geographically dispersed stations exhibit similar pollution patterns based on the underlying data structure.

The second objective broadens the scope to include six pollutants: NO_2 , PM_{10} , $PM_{2.5}$, O_3 , CO , and SO_2 , using data from 60 monitoring stations between 2018 and 2020. Both the conventional Mapper and Ball Mapper algorithms are applied to generate topological graphs that capture the dynamic patterns of each pollutant based on the data shape.

Finally, the third objective focuses on a comparative analysis of the topological graphs generated by the conventional Mapper and Ball Mapper algorithms. Graph invariants, such as Graph Density, Fragmentation Index, Estrada Index, and Node Degree Distribution, are used to evaluate the structural characteristics of topological graphs. These metrics are used to assess

which of the two algorithms, the Conventional Mapper or the Ball Mapper, better represents the behavior of each pollutant based on domain knowledge and literature. Additionally, the visualization and interpretability of topological graphs are compared with those generated by a traditional HACA dendrogram.

1.7 Significance of Study

This thesis aims to develop an efficient qualitative air quality analysis tool that can assist the Department of Environment (DOE) in identifying potential redundancies in monitoring stations and considering reallocations to more critical areas, thereby improving coverage and effectiveness. By leveraging topological structures, this study examines the potential for adopting a centralized approach to pollution control, based on stations clustered in a node and those in connected nodes.

TDA has the potential to provide valuable insights into evaluating the effectiveness of environmental policies, such as emission regulations, by analyzing changes in pollutant dynamics over time. By comparing topological graph structures before and after policy implementation, this approach may help identify whether pollutant behavior stabilizes, improves, or reverts to its previous pattern once the policies are no longer in effect. Additionally, this research offers an alternative perspective for environmental scientists and mathematicians interested in exploring new approaches to air quality research and management. Finally, it also provides qualitative insights that complement traditional statistical methods. Combining these approaches could help policymakers develop a more comprehensive understanding of air quality dynamics, contributing to more informed and evidence-based decision-making.

1.8 Thesis Outline

This thesis is structured into six comprehensive chapters, each contributing to a detailed exploration of air quality analysis through the traditional clustering method, HACA, and TDA

techniques, namely, CM and BM algorithms. Chapter 2 offers an extensive literature review, focusing on the application of traditional HACA in air quality studies. It also explores the use of TDA techniques, including the CM and BM algorithms, across various scientific fields, providing a solid foundation for their application in this research. Chapter 3 introduces the air quality datasets used in the study, along with a detailed explanation of the methodologies and algorithms employed in the analysis. Chapter 4 presents the results from the analysis, providing interpretations that align with the research objectives. In Chapter 5, these findings are discussed in the context of the study's objectives, emphasizing their significance and addressing the limitations encountered during the study. The thesis concludes with Chapter 6, which synthesizes the key insights and offers recommendations for future research, paving the way for further exploration in the field of air quality management.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This chapter presents a literature review structured into four sections, providing a comprehensive overview of the methodologies employed in topological data analysis for air quality studies. Section 2.2 provides an overview of the hierarchical agglomerative clustering analysis (HACA) approach, summarizing its applications and contributions to air quality data analysis. Section 2.3 reviews the applications of TDA as a qualitative analysis approach across various fields, highlighting its potential as a valuable tool for analyzing air quality datasets. This is followed by a review of its tools, including CM and BM techniques. Additionally, Subsection 2.3.1 reviews studies that utilize the CM algorithm, highlighting its specific role and effectiveness in identifying patterns within a dataset. Finally, Section 2.3.2 explores the application and performance of the BM algorithm, highlighting its effectiveness in generating a simplified and enhanced visual representation of datasets. The chapter concludes in Section 2.4 with a discussion of the research motivations.

2.2 Traditional HACA in Analysing Air Quality Data

According to Govender and Sivakumar (2020), clustering is a data analysis technique used to explore and identify patterns in the underlying structure of a dataset by grouping data points with similar characteristics. Over the years, clustering techniques have been widely utilized in atmospheric science, with significant applications in climate and meteorological studies (Pampuch et al., 2023; Handhayani & Lewenusa, 2024). This technique groups data points into homogeneous clusters based on proximity measures derived from temporal information (Mehta et al., 2020). Numerous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of cluster analysis in examining spatial patterns of air quality monitoring sites. For instance, Zhao et al. (2016)

proposed a trajectory clustering method that effectively identifies hotspots within trajectory data, providing valuable insights for urban transportation planning and management.

Additionally, Vasudha and Rao (2023) applied HACA to classify air pollution monitoring stations in India into four distinct clusters based on average Air Quality Index (AQI) levels, highlighting the significant impact of topographical conditions on air pollution patterns. Alia et al. (2022) effectively classified air quality monitoring stations in Peninsular Malaysia based on the pollutant distribution using HACA. Zhang and Yang (2022) employed HACA to identify trends in PM_{2.5} pollution and regional divisions across China, thereby aiding in the development of coordinated control measures for clean air policies. Stolz et al. (2020) optimized air quality monitoring stations in Mexico by identifying redundant stations. Xu et al. (2022) classified Chinese cities according to pollution levels, revealing the most and least polluted areas. Other significant studies include works by Lu et al. (2011), Zhang et al. (2016), Pires et al. (2008), Jorquera and Villalobos (2020), Rahman et al. (2022), Fang et al. (2022), and Suris et al. (2022).

While traditional HACA approaches have been successful in analyzing air pollutant behavior, interpreting the relationships between clusters can be challenging. The HACA dendrogram can sometimes be difficult to interpret, particularly when working with high-dimensional datasets, where inter-cluster relationships may be unclear, as observed by Ezugwu et al. (2020), Ran et al. (2022), and Huang et al. (2021). These challenges associated with interpreting high-dimensional datasets highlight the need for alternative approaches, particularly qualitative methods that can offer clearer and more intuitive visualizations of clusters and their interrelationships. To address limitations in traditional HACA, several studies have explored modified approaches. Particularly in air quality studies, Zulkepli et al. (2022) proposed a hybridization of HACA with persistent homology to assess haze-related air pollution in Southeast Asia. By replacing Euclidean distance with Wasserstein distance and incorporating persistent homology, the method captures deeper spatial structures. Results show

improved clustering accuracy and more precise identification of patterns in elevated particulate matter levels compared to traditional HACA.

Finally, traditional HACA can be used as a clustering algorithm within the conventional Mapper framework to extract qualitative insights from complex datasets based on their shape. However, despite the effectiveness of this method it remains insufficiently applied in air quality research as evidenced by the existing literature. This highlights a contextual methodological gap in applying topological data analysis tools, particularly the Mapper algorithm, within the field of air quality research.

2.3 Topological Data Analysis (TDA) in Environmental Studies

TDA is an emerging field that leverages concepts from algebraic topology to analyze the shape and underlying structure of datasets (Carlsson, 2020). Its growing application across various studies provides fresh insights and innovative methods for data analysis (Corcoran & Jones, 2023). TDA, being a qualitative approach, highlights the topological features within datasets, revealing insights that traditional quantitative methods might overlook (Musa et al., 2021).

The ability of TDA to uncover hidden patterns and shapes in a dataset emphasizes the importance of qualitative approaches that focus on the topological and geometric structures within a dataset. Rather than relying solely on quantitative and numerical summaries, which do not capture the inherent shapes in a dataset. As shown in Figure 2.1, point clouds such as a dinosaur, circle, bullseye, wide lines, star, horizontal lines, scattered dots, and cross each have distinct shapes; yet, when analyzed using traditional quantitative methods, they yielded similar summary statistics. For example, each of the datasets has the same X Mean of 54.26, Y Mean of 47.83, X Standard Deviation of 16.76, Y Standard Deviation of 26.93, and a correlation of -0.06 . This similarity in summary statistics, despite vastly different shapes, was observed by Matejka and Fitzmaurice (2017) and further examined by Gillespie et al. (2024).

Figure 2.1 Datasaurus dozen (Gillespie et al., 2024)

TDA can capture complex patterns and relationships within a dataset that may be hidden by similar statistical values, enabling a deeper understanding of the dataset's structure. The TDA approach has proven to be effective in various fields of research. For instance, Chazal and Michel (2021) utilized TDA persistent homology to analyze high-dimensional biological data, including gene expression and protein interaction networks. Pereira et al. (2021) applied TDA Mapper to investigate the resilience of social networks. Hernández-Lemus et al. (2024) explored the application of TDA persistent homology in analyzing cardiovascular signals, highlighting its potential to improve understanding of cardiovascular diseases and their treatment. El-Yaagoubi et al. (2023) introduced TDA persistent homology concepts to a statistical audience, presenting an approach for analyzing multivariate time series data. Skaf and Laubenbacher (2022) reviewed emerging mathematical methods, including TDA, to enhance the ability of clinicians and researchers to analyze biomedical data. Finally, Uray et al. (2024) conducted a comprehensive survey on the applications of TDA in industrial production and manufacturing settings, as well as in other areas.

TDA has also been applied to various environmental science studies. For example, Islambekov et al. (2019) demonstrated that integrating persistent homology with existing change-point detection algorithms enhances the accuracy of identifying distributional regime

shifts in environmental time series. Similarly, Ofori-Boateng et al. (2021) applied TDA persistent homology to compare aerosol optical depth (AOD) maps across varying spatial resolutions, revealing its strength in systematically evaluating spatial patterns without the need for resampling. Using AOD datasets from the Goddard Earth Observing System, this study highlights the applicability of TDA in Earth science studies. Additionally, Munch (2017) illustrated how TDA outputs, such as persistence diagrams and conventional Mapper topological graphs, enable quantification of shape and structure in data, making these techniques accessible to researchers in education, learning sciences, and various scientific domains. TDA persistent homology has been applied to the detection of early warning signals and floods (Musa et al., 2021; Ohanuba et al., 2021), as well as in the clustering of rainfall stations (Gobithaasan et al., 2022).

Recently, Zulkepli et al. (2022) utilized persistent homology to analyze air quality data, identifying the most and least polluted areas during haze events by extracting topological features. The study builds on earlier work by Zulkepli et al. (2020). Overall, the literature on TDA application in environmental studies remains limited despite its significant potential to address environmental challenges and handle high-volume data generated through environmental monitoring. TDA offers promising opportunities for deriving new insights through topological representations. This thesis aims to apply TDA tools, specifically the conventional Mapper and its variant the Ball Mapper algorithm to analyze air quality datasets.

2.3.1 Conventional Mapper (CM)

The CM algorithm proposed by Singh et al. (2007) has become a powerful tool in TDA for visualizing high-dimensional datasets. It transforms complex datasets into simplified topological graphs composed of nodes and edges, thereby creating a simpler representation of the dataset (Munch, 2017). As shown in Figure 2.2, each node represents a cluster of points with similar characteristics, while the edges connecting nodes indicate subtle relationships

between points in the connected clusters. Node colors are assigned based on specific attributes or features of interest, enabling the visualization of additional insights into patterns within the dataset.

Figure 2.2 Example of a topological graph

The CM algorithm approach requires multiple parameters to be set up, including the filter function, cover, overlap percentage, and clustering algorithm, to produce topological graphs (Geniesse et al., 2019). CM has been successfully applied in various research areas, including the spread of coronavirus (Chen & Volić, 2021), medicine (Caputi et al., 2021), core gene expression (Palande et al., 2023), and mapping technological spaces (Escolar et al., 2020). These applications demonstrate the CM algorithm ability to uncover hidden patterns and inter-cluster relationships that are often limited in traditional methods, making it a promising tool for air quality analysis.

The CM algorithm enhances traditional clustering techniques by offering a qualitative visualization of clustering results, representing the dataset as a topological graph. This approach provides a clearer understanding of complex datasets by simplifying them into nodes and edges, revealing patterns and relationships that may not be evident through conventional methods. This thesis aims to leverage the CM algorithm to provide a novel qualitative perspective on air pollutant data, enhance air quality monitoring management, and support decision-makers in formulating more effective pollution control strategies.

2.3.2 Ball Mapper (BM)

Recently, Dłotko (2019) introduced BM, a variant of the CM technique in TDA. BM, a more straightforward topological and geometric-based approach, captures the shape of the dataset by grouping neighborhood points using balls of equal radius through a greedy or Max-min algorithm without relying on a rigid clustering algorithm to produce a topological graph. Nodes are connected by edges when their respective balls intersect, indicating shared members. This approach yields a topological graph, similar to CM, where nodes represent clusters of similar data points (Dłotko et al., 2024). Unlike the CM algorithm which requires multiple parameters the BM algorithm uses a single parameter, the ball radius which is use as a cover in the algorithm. This improvement makes BM easier to implement while still providing a rich informational output.

Current studies that utilize the BM algorithm include Rudkin et al. (2023), which employed the BM algorithm to analyze regional voting behavior in the UK's Brexit referendum. Their study revealed that Leave votes were more geographically concentrated and homogeneous compared to “Remain” votes. The findings, consistent across different administrative levels, provided new insights into the regional economic and cultural factors influencing Brexit, demonstrating the effectiveness of BM in uncovering hidden spatial voting patterns. Dłotko et al. (2021) also employed the algorithm to visualize complex, non-monotonic relationships between key financial ratios and stock returns. It reveals hidden structures in asset pricing, illustrates how machine learning models capture return patterns, and identifies segments with significant abnormal returns, demonstrating the BM potential to reveal shape, connectivity, and spatial relationships within a dataset. However, the literature on BM is still emerging, and its full capabilities are yet to be extensively explored. The BM technique provides a clear and insightful approach to understanding complex datasets, effectively revealing inherent relationships and patterns within the data (Rudkin et al., 2023).

2.4 Motivation of the Study

The motivation for this study lies in exploring the potential of TDA tools, notably the CM and BM algorithms, in environmental science, where they remain underutilized despite their demonstrated potential. Also, the TDA qualitative approach offers a unique perspective on complex data, highlighting structural and relational patterns that traditional quantitative methods often overlook. While persistent homology has shown success in environmental studies and recently in air quality analysis, there is limited research on CM and BM specifically within the context of air pollutant behavior. The CM and BM methodologies discussed in Chapter 3 enable a simplified yet informative visualization of high-dimensional datasets, which we believe will provide air quality researchers and managers with an alternative tool for monitoring and understanding pollutant patterns.

CHAPTER 3

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

Figure 3.1 is the flowchart of the methodology employed in this thesis. The process begins with data acquisition and pre-processing, as presented in Section 3.2, followed by both qualitative and quantitative approaches. The TDA method, discussed in Section 3.3, comprises two techniques: the CM and BM algorithms. The first objective is addressed by applying the CM algorithm presented in Section 3.3.3 to construct topological graphs. These CM topological graphs aim to elucidate the yearly behavior of PM_{10} concentrations while capturing the underlying topological structure among air quality monitoring stations.

The second objective focuses on the application of the BM algorithm, a variant of CM, to construct alternative topological graphs of NO_2 , PM_{10} , $PM_{2.5}$, O_3 , CO , and SO_2 . By employing the BM algorithm discussed in Section 3.3.4, the study aims to provide a complementary lens through which to present and interpret air quality dynamics. The resulting BM topological graph is analyzed in the context of its structural and visual expressiveness.

In Objective Three, a comparative analysis of the CM and BM topological graphs constructed using the corresponding datasets will be implemented, utilizing the graph invariants discussed in Section 3.3.5. Also, the visualization of the topological graphs is compared against the HACA dendrogram. This comparative analysis evaluates the relative strengths and limitations of each method in presenting and interpreting the clustering behavior of air monitoring stations.

Figure 3.1 Research Methodology Flowchart

3.2 Datasets

The datasets used in this study are secondary data obtained from the Department of Environment (DOE) Malaysia (DOE, 2024). These data are collected from 60 air quality monitoring stations across the six regions, namely Northern, Central, Eastern, Southern, Sabah, and Sarawak in Malaysia. These stations are strategically located in the urban, suburban, rural, and industrial areas. Figure 3.2 presents a map of Malaysia, illustrating the locations of these stations, with different colors indicating the regional categorizations. The names of these stations, with their respective index number, are listed in Table 3.1. These categorizations serve

as labels in the topological graph to investigate the interrelation of cluster similarities within the context of geographical relationships.

Figure 3.2 Location of 60 air quality monitoring stations across Malaysia.

Table 3.1 List of 60 air quality monitoring stations in Figure 3.2

No.	Station	No.	Station	No.	Station
1	Pasir_Gudang	21	Bintulu	41	Kuala_Selangor
2	Kemaman	22	Miri	42	Keningau
3	Perai	23	Sarikei	43	Sandakan
4	Kuching	24	Kota_Kinabalu	44	Putrajaya
5	Bukit_Rambai	25	Limbang	45	Cheras
6	Jerantut	26	Langkawi	46	Kapit
7	Tasek	27	Kangar	47	Port_Dickson
8	Seberang_Jaya	28	Kuala_Terengganu	48	Kota_Tinggi
9	Nilai	29	Samarahan	49	Batu_Muda
10	Klang	30	Sri_Aman	50	Tanah_Merah
11	Kuantan	31	USM	51	Banting
12	Balok_Baru	32	Tawau	52	ILP_Miri
13	Petaling_Jaya	33	Alor_Setar	53	Balik_Pulau
14	Sungai_Petani	34	Seri_Manjung	54	Batu_Pahat
15	Larkin	35	Labuan	55	Besut
16	Taiping	36	Bandaraya_Melaka	56	Indera
17	Kota_Bharu	37	Muar	57	Segamat
18	Paka	38	Tanjung_Malim	58	Kimanis
19	Shah_Alam	39	Pegoh	59	Temerloh
20	Sibu	40	Seremban	60	Kulim

The DOE monitors six major air pollutants nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), particulate matter with diameters less than 10 micrometers (PM₁₀), particulate matter with diameters less than 2.5 micrometers (PM_{2.5}), ozone (O₃), carbon monoxide (CO), and sulfur dioxide (SO₂) across 60 designated air quality monitoring stations, as listed in Table 3.1. This thesis examined the daily average of PM10 datasets from selected years (2012, 2013, 2014, 2015, 2018, 2019, and 2020).

However, the 2016 and 2017 datasets were excluded from the analysis because they had over 20% missing data. Also, the datasets containing average daily concentrations for all six pollutants (NO₂, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, O₃, CO, and SO₂) from 2018 to 2020 are utilized.

In Malaysia, the DOE reports air quality using the Air Pollution Index (API), a measure that communicates air quality levels to the public. The API summarizes the concentrations of various pollutants into a single number, providing a clear and straightforward way to understand air pollution levels and their potential health effects. Based on the air quality status supplied by the DOE in the Environmental Quality Report 2020 (DOE, 2024), the API status is categorized into five classes, as shown in Table 3.2.

Table 3.2 Air Pollution Index (API)

API	Air Quality Status
0-50	Good
51-100	Moderate
101-200	Unhealthy
201-300	Very unhealthy
>300	Hazardous

Based on the API status, Unhealthy days occur when pollutant concentrations significantly exceed the limits set by the Malaysian Ambient Air Quality Guidelines (MAAQG). These guidelines establish specific thresholds for the daily average concentrations of various pollutants, providing a benchmark to assess the air quality on public health. As shown in Table 3.3, pollutant levels that exceed the benchmark may pose potential health risks to the public.

Table 3.3 Ambient Air Quality Guidelines (MAAQG) levels

Pollutant	Unhealthy Threshold level
PM ₁₀	100 µg/m ³ (24-hour average)
PM _{2.5}	35 µg/m ³ (24-hour average)
SO ₂	0.03 ppm (24-hour average)
NO ₂	0.05 ppm (24-hour average)
CO	8.75 ppm (8-hour average)
O ₃	0.05 ppm (8-hour average)

Based on the air quality dataset described in this section, this thesis employs TDA techniques to explore the underlying shape and patterns within the dataset qualitatively. The following section introduces the fundamental concepts of topological data analysis.

3.3 Topological Data Analysis (TDA)

TDA is a framework that applies principles from algebraic topology to study the shape of data. It emphasizes the properties of spaces and shapes that are invariant under continuous transformations such as stretching or bending. To formally introduce the basic concepts in TDA, it begins with the definition of a topology (Definition 3.1) and topological space (Definition 3.2), which provides the mathematical framework for studying shape and structure.

Definition 3.1 *Topology τ is the mathematical study of properties of spaces and shapes that remain unchanged under continuous transformations, such as stretching, bending, and twisting, while excluding alterations like tearing or gluing (John, 2020). This provides the foundational language for analyzing geometric and spatial relationships in TDA. With the notion of topology established, a topological space is formally defined as follows:*

Definition 3.2 *A topological space (X, τ) is a set X equipped with a topology τ , where τ is a collection of subsets of X , called open sets that satisfy the following axioms (Sakai, 2020):*

1. $\emptyset \in \tau$ and $X \in \tau$
2. τ is closed under arbitrary union: For any index set A if $\{U_\alpha\}_{\alpha \in A} \subseteq \tau$, then: $\bigcup_{\alpha \in A} U_\alpha \in \tau$
3. τ is closed under finite intersection: if U_1, U_2, \dots, U_n are sets in τ , then: $\bigcap_i^n U_i \in \tau$.

The basic building blocks in TDA are simplices, the geometric objects that generalize points, line segments, and triangles to arbitrary dimensions, with definitions provided below:

Definition 3.3 *a simplex is the simplest possible shape in a given dimension, serving as the foundation of a simplicial complex (Barrabés & Mateu-Figueras, 2006). For instance, a 0-*

simplex represents a point, a 1-simplex an edge, and a 2-simplex a filled triangle, as illustrated in Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3 Examples of simplices in different dimensions

Topological summaries of high-dimensional datasets are constructed using various tools in TDA that reveal the underlying structure or “shape” of the data. Among these tools, the Mapper algorithm is commonly used to transform high-dimensional data into simplified graphical representations. This method enables visual interpretation of patterns, relationships, and clusters within the dataset. The following section introduces the conventional Mapper algorithm and provides a brief discussion on its topological and statistical versions.

3.3.1 Conventional Mapper (CM) Algorithm

The CM algorithm was first introduced by Singh et al. (2007) and further developed by Nicolau et al. (2011). Over time, it has gained significant attention and has been successfully applied across various domains, as highlighted by Lum et al. (2013). It is a pivotal method within TDA. It offers an approach to visualizing the topological structure of high-dimensional datasets or point clouds by employing multiple parameters, such as filter function, cover, overlap percentage, and clustering algorithm, to produce a simpler dataset representation. The entire algorithm is fundamentally built on partially clustering the data, guided by a collection of functions defined over it. To construct topological summaries of data, the nerve of a covering based on the Nerve Theorem discussed in Section 3.3.1(a) is used to capture the overlap structure among the collection of subsets.

3.3.1(a) The Nerve Theorem

The Nerve Theorem states that if a topological space is covered by a finite collection of open sets whose finite intersections are all contractible (i.e., it can be continuously transformed without tearing and gluing), then the nerve of that cover forms a simplicial complex (Definition 3.3) that is homotopy equivalent to X . This theorem provides the mathematical foundation for the CM algorithm, ensuring that the topological graph (simplicial complex) constructed from overlapping preimages reflects the approximate shape of the data at a simplified resolution. It justifies the CM topological graph as an insightful summary of high-dimensional data by preserving topological features, such as connectedness and loops (Singh et al., 2007). Definition 3.4 offers the formal construction of a nerve, thereby supporting this claim (Boonpok & Viriyapong, 2022).

Definition 3.4 *Given a covering $\mathcal{U} = \{U_\alpha\}_{\alpha \in A}$ of a topological space X , the nerve of the cover \mathcal{U} , denoted as $N(\mathcal{U})$ is the simplicial complex (also known as the Čech complex), whose vertex set corresponds to the index set A with a finite subset $\{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \dots, \alpha_n\} \subseteq A$ that span $(n-1)$ simplex in $N(\mathcal{U})$ if and only if*

$$U_{\alpha_1} \cap U_{\alpha_2} \cap \dots \cap U_{\alpha_n} \neq \emptyset. \quad (1)$$

The simplices represent collections of subsets within \mathcal{U} that share at least one common point (i.e., have a non-empty intersection), forming a simplicial complex. The nerve construction is effective for analyzing discrete point clouds and extends its usefulness to more general contexts involving arbitrary topological spaces. As shown in Figure 3.4, where the point cloud X with subsets $U \subset X$ with $\alpha_i \in U$, where α_i are the points in X , U are covered with \mathcal{U} , forming 0-simplex (vertex), 1-simplexes (vertices with an edge), and 2-simplex (vertices with a hole) collectively forming a nerve $N(\mathcal{U})$ which is homotopic to X . The following section presents the CM algorithm as an approximation of the Reeb graph (Definition 3.5).

Figure 3.4 Nerve construction from a point cloud and its associated simplicial complex

3.3.1 (b) Reeb Graph

In topological data analysis, the Reeb graph plays a critical role in summarizing the structure of a topological space to a scalar function. It captures how level sets of the function evolve, merge, or split, offering a simplified yet informative representation of the underlying space. The concept serves as the theoretical foundation for the Mapper algorithm, which generalizes Reeb graphs to discrete data. The formal definition is presented as follows:

Definition 3.5: *Given a topological space M and a continuous real-valued function $f : M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, the Reeb graph identifies the level set of f at value c , $f^{-1}(c) = \{m \in M \mid f(m) = c\}$, representing all points with the same function values. Each connected component of a level set is collapsed into a single point, forming nodes. The edges connecting the nodes represent how the components merge or split as the function value changes (Carrière et al., 2017).*

Figure 3.5 is the construction of a Reeb graph from a torus. When the target parameter space is one-dimensional, the resulting construction can be interpreted as a stochastic or discrete approximation of the Reeb graph (Definition 3.5). The conventional Mapper graph approximates the Reeb graph by clustering data points according to a chosen filter function and connecting these clusters based on their overlaps. Hence, the Reeb graph is a continuous object from a continuous function, while the Mapper graph is a discrete, data-driven version of a Reeb graph as discussed in Sections 3.3.1(c) and 3.3.1(d). Conversely, the construction recovers the Reeb graph with a sufficiently refined covering (Singh et al., 2007).

Figure 3.5 Reeb graph construction for a Torus using a height function

3.3.1 (c) The Topological Version of CM

The topological formulation of the CM algorithm is rooted in the theory of simplicial complexes and the Nerve Theorem. This version emphasizes the mathematical structure of the CM topological graph, treating it as a simplicial complex induced by the pullback of a covering under a continuous map. The following definition formalizes this construction.

Definition 3.6 Let X and X^* be topological spaces and $f : X \rightarrow X^*$ be a continuous map. Let $U = \{U_\alpha\}_{\alpha \in A}$ be a finite open set covering X^* then consider $f^*(U) = \{f^{-1}(U_\alpha)\}_{\alpha \in A}$ the covering of X where $\{f^{-1}(U_\alpha)\}_{\alpha \in A}$ is called the pullback of U along f . Then the CM topological graph G is defined to be the nerve or simplicial complex on the index set A (Singh et al. 2007).

$$G(U, f) = N(f^*(U)) = \left\{ \sigma \subseteq A : \bigcap_{\alpha \in \sigma} f^{-1}(U_\alpha) \neq \emptyset \right\}. \quad (2)$$

σ represents a subset of the pullback cover $f^*(U_\alpha)$.

A collection of simplices σ forms the nerve or topological graph if the intersection of all preimages $f^{-1}(U_\alpha)$ for $\alpha \in \sigma$ is non-empty. Under appropriate conditions (e.g., good covers), the Nerve Theorem guarantees that the nerve or the topological graph is homotopy equivalent to the shape, providing a topological summary of the structure induced by the continuous map f (Bui et al. 2020). This definition is critical for understanding how Mapper

encodes the shape of data into a topological graph. Section 3.3.3(a) discusses the implementation of the data-driven Mapper algorithm.

3.3.1 (d) The Statistical Version of CM

In constructing a CM topological graph, four steps are followed with parameter selection and setup as shown in Figure 3.6, where the parameters such as the filter function, the clustering algorithm, the setup of the cover, and the percentage overlaps of the covers are determined (Singh et al. 2007). The filter function is used to discriminate the characteristics of the data. Next, the filtered range is organized into overlapping bins called covers. A specified overlap percentage determines the extent to which these covers overlap. A clustering algorithm is then applied to the pullback of the data points within each cover based on their proximity. This process produces a topological graph homotopic to the original dataset, that is, a simplified representation of a high-dimensional dataset. In this graph, nodes represent the clustered data points, and edges indicate nodes that share common data points based on the specified overlap percentage.

Figure 3.6 Conventional Mapper Flowchart

Given a dataset or a point cloud $X \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ consisting of a collection of points, the steps for constructing a CM topological graph are as follows:

Step 1: Choose a filter or lens function, $f : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ to discriminate the characteristics of the dataset by projecting $X \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ to a lower Euclidean space, \mathbb{R}^d where $(d < n)$.

Dimension reduction methods, such as principal component analysis (PCA), t-distributed stochastic neighbor embedding (t-SNE), and uniform manifold approximation projection (UMAP), can be used as filter functions. In this work, PCA is used as the filter function. In the Mapper algorithm, a multivariate time series is interpreted as a point cloud by treating each time step as a vector in \mathbb{R}^d , where d is the number of variables; thus, the entire series forms a set of high-dimensional vectors representing the system's state over time.

Figure 3.7 presents a flowchart illustrating the PCA process, which is used as a filter function for dimensionality reduction. PCA is commonly used in air pollution studies in combination with HACA (Behera et al., 2021; Malav et al., 2022). These two parameters are used because they have been confirmed in the literature as the most adopted methods used in the Mapper algorithm. The process begins with inputting a high-dimensional dataset consisting of M observations and N features or variables. The data is then standardized using Z -score normalization, which centers the data by subtracting the mean and scales it to unit variance to create an adjusted matrix X . The covariance matrix C is computed to understand the relationships between variables, followed by the calculation of eigenvalues and eigenvectors to identify the magnitude and direction of data variance. The eigenvectors are sorted in descending order based on their corresponding eigenvalues, and the top eigenvectors are selected for dimensionality reduction. Finally, the reduced-dimensional matrix is generated by multiplying the normalized dataset by the chosen eigenvectors, resulting in a lower-dimensional representation of the data that preserves the most significant variance.

Figure 3.7 Flowchart of the PCA algorithm

Step 2: Build a cover on the image of the discriminated values through a dimension-reduced function $f(X)$, with a collection of open sets, $(U_i)_{i \in I}$ where I is a finite indexing set. Typically, the set $(U_i)_{i \in I}$ is composed of overlapping Covers (products of intervals), and at this stage, it is essential to determine the percentage of overlap.

Step 3: For each interval or cover U_i , cluster the points in the preimage $f^{-1}(U_i)$ by utilizing a suitable clustering algorithm such as HACA, DBSCAN, or K-Means, to form a set of clusters C_{i_n} . n is the cluster index or the number of clusters in each cover U_i . The HACA algorithm flowchart is illustrated in Figure 3.8, where the process begins with each data point as an individual cluster and iteratively merges the closest pairs of clusters based on the Euclidean distance. The merging of clusters is conducted using the complete linkage method, which defines the distance between two clusters as the maximum distance between any single pair of

elements from each cluster. This approach ensures the formation of compact and similarly sized clusters, with the process continuing until the dataset is divided into exactly four clusters.

Figure 3.8 HACA Flowchart

Step 4: Formation of the CM topological graph. Each cluster C_{i_n} forms node N , and for any $i \leq j \leq I$ if clusters C_{i_n} and C_{j_p} share the same data points and overlap, that is if $C_{i_n} \cap C_{j_p} \neq \emptyset$ then an edge E (a line) is drawn connecting the two nodes N , if otherwise, singleton nodes are formed, yielding a topological graph $G=(N,E)$. Example 3.1 provides an example of

constructing a conventional Mapper topological graph using an arbitrary point cloud. In this work, the CM algorithm is implemented using Python, following the guidelines outlined in the KeplerMapper documentation (van Veen et al., 2019). This approach demonstrates a practical application of the CM algorithm in representing and visualizing high-dimensional datasets.

Example 3.1

Given a P-shaped point cloud $X \subset \mathbb{R}^2$, as illustrated in Figure 3.9, this example demonstrates the implementation of the CM algorithm to generate a corresponding CM topological graph. Firstly, the point cloud X is discriminated and projected onto a one-dimensional space along the y -axis using a filter function $f: X \rightarrow X^*$ where $X^* \subset \mathbb{R}$ and subsequently covered with open sets $U_i = \{U_1, U_2, U_3, \dots, U_9\}$ with each cover overlapping in an equal percentage, as shown in Steps 1-2 of Figure 3.3. In Step 3, clustering is then performed on the preimages or pullback of U_i , $f^{-1}(U_i)$ to have C_i , where U_1, U_2 , corresponds to C_1, C_2, \dots . If $C_1 \cap C_2 \neq \emptyset$ then an edge E is formed by connecting the nodes N formed by C_1 and C_2 . However, if $C_1 \cap C_2 = \emptyset$ then C_1 and C_2 forms two singleton nodes. From the collection of nodes N and edges E In Step 4, a CM topological graph $G(N, E)$ is produced. In the following sections, the BM algorithm, a variant of the CM algorithm, is discussed.

Figure 3.9 Toy P-shape point cloud used in illustrating CM algorithm implementation.

3.3.4 Ball Mapper (BM) Algorithm

The BM algorithm, introduced by Dlotko (2019), is a TDA tool and a variant of the CM algorithm. The BM algorithm uses a collection of closed balls, relying on a single parameter, $\varepsilon > 0$, that is, the radius centered at an arbitrary point $c_i \in X$ to cover all the points in the dataset based on the Max-min or greedy algorithm, as described by Dlotko et al. (2021), and to cluster all data points into subsets within the dataset. Unlike the CM algorithm, which requires multiple parameters to construct a topological graph, the BM algorithm only requires the radius of the ball. This ball serves as a cover for grouping data points based on similarity.

In the BM algorithm, nodes are formed from the points clustered within each ball, and edges are created between nodes if their corresponding balls intersect, thereby producing a topological graph. This simplified approach reduces complexity in managing multiple parameters by focusing solely on the ball radius, making it easier to implement while still capturing the topological representation of the dataset. Figure 3.10 is the flowchart of the BM algorithm. A detailed discussion of how the balls form a cover to cluster data points is presented in the following subsections.

Figure 3.10 Ball Mapper Flowchart

Definition 3.8 Let $X \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ where X denote a dataset or point cloud covered with a collection of closed balls of radius $\varepsilon > 0$ centered at a landmark point $c_i \in X$. The balls are formed with

c_i as the centroid, which is used to build an ε -net based on a Max-min or greedy algorithm to cover the entire X .

Step 1: Cover (Ball); given a point cloud X , using greedy ε -net algorithm to construct a cover for X using a closed ball by selecting a landmark point $c_i \in X$, where each point $x_i \in X$ is within a radius. Each closed ball $B_\varepsilon(c_i) = \{x_i \in X : d(x_i, c_i) \leq \varepsilon\}$, centered at a point c_i , contains all points in X that lie within a distance d between ε and c_i .

In this thesis, the distance metric d used is cosine similarity, which allows each ball to cover points based on their similarity. For points $(c, p) \in B_\varepsilon$ where the points c and p are vectors, the cosine similarity between them is defined as:

$$\text{Cosine similarity} = \cos(\theta) = \frac{\mathbf{c} \cdot \mathbf{p}}{\|\mathbf{c}\| \|\mathbf{p}\|}. \quad (3.0)$$

The corresponding cosine distance is defined as (Hbaieb et al., 2021; Prasudha et al., 2024):

$$d(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{p}_i) = 1 - \cos(\theta). \quad (3.1)$$

Using the greedy or Max-min algorithm ε -net approach, this implies that a ball centered at c will include all points p_i such that:

$$d(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{p}_i) \leq \varepsilon. \quad (3.2)$$

Two balls are centered at c_i and c_j with radius ε is said to overlap if:

$$d(c_i, c_j) = 1 - \cos(\theta) \leq 2\varepsilon, \quad (3.3)$$

The corresponding overlap balls are given as:

$$B_\varepsilon(c_i, \varepsilon) \cap B_\varepsilon(c_j, \varepsilon) \neq \emptyset. \quad (3.4)$$

The minimum center-to-center distance between two overlapping balls A and B is given as:

$$d(A, B) \geq \varepsilon. \quad (3.5)$$

where ε the radius of the balls is the only parameter required to construct the BM topological graph. This approach ensured that all points in X are covered by balls of radius ε allowing effective representation of the point cloud X .

Step 2: BM Topological Graph; the collection of balls $\{B_\varepsilon(c_i), B_\varepsilon(c_j), \dots, B_\varepsilon(c_n)\}$ covered the entire point cloud X . Each ball represents a node N . If two balls are centered at c_i and c_j , denoted by $B_\varepsilon(c_i)$ and $B_\varepsilon(c_j)$, have a non-empty intersection, i.e., $B_\varepsilon(c_i) \cap B_\varepsilon(c_j) \neq \emptyset$, an edge E is formed between the corresponding nodes. The collection of the nodes and edges produces a Ball Mapper topological graph $G=(N, E)$. In the following discussion, a summary of the Greedy algorithm, the Max-Min algorithm, and the BM algorithm is presented, as outlined by Dłotko (2019).

The size of the nodes in the topological graph reflects the number of data points clustered within each node, determined by the radius of the balls used in the algorithm. Larger nodes indicate clusters with more data points, while smaller nodes represent clusters with fewer data points. This work implements the BM algorithm using the pyBallMapper Python library (Gurnari, 2022) to visualize the topological structures. This implementation ensures effective visualization and analysis, enabling simpler representation of the dataset. A summary of the algorithms used in the implementation of the BM graph is given as follows:

Algorithm 1: Greedy Algorithm ε -net for Selecting Cover Centres in Ball Mapper

Input: Point cloud X , $\varepsilon > 0$

All points $x_i \in X$ as not covered.

Initialize $B(X, \varepsilon)$ empty cover vector.

Repeat:

Pick the first point $c \in X$ that is not covered as the centroid.

For every point in $x \in B(c, \varepsilon) \cap X$, add p to $B(X, \varepsilon)[x]$

Keep adjusting the ε until all the data points in X are well covered.

Keep adjusting the ε until all the data points in X are well covered.

Return $B(X, \varepsilon)$

Algorithm 2: Max-Min Algorithm ε -net for Selecting Cover Centres in Ball Mapper

Input: Point cloud X , $\varepsilon > 0$

Pick an arbitrary point. $c \in X$; initialize $B = \{c\}$

Build a cluster or ball. $B(c, \varepsilon)$.

Repeat:

Find point $c' \in X \setminus B$ within a distance $d(c', B) \geq \varepsilon$

Add c' to B

Form ball $B(c', \varepsilon)$.

Until $d \leq \varepsilon$., all points in X are within distance ε of at least one centre in B

Return $B(X, \varepsilon)$.

Algorithm 3: Ball Mapper Algorithm for Constructing Topological Graph

Input: Cover vector $B(X, \varepsilon)$ from Max-min or Greedy Algorithm $\varepsilon > 0$

$N =$ cover elements in $B(X, \varepsilon)$, $E = \emptyset$, for every point $x \in X$ do

For every pair of cover elements $c_1 \cap c_2 \neq \emptyset$ in $B(X, \varepsilon)[x]$, draw an edge between nodes N

corresponding to the cover elements c_1 and c_2 implying $E = E \cup \{c_1, c_2\}$

Return $G(N, E)$.

Example 3.2

Figure 3.12 illustrates the construction of a BM topological graph, following the algorithm discussed in Section 3.6, using the same P-shape point cloud X . A collection of closed balls of equal radius $\varepsilon > 0$ covers the point cloud, centered on randomly selected landmarks $c_i \in X$, where the point c_i is randomly chosen as the center of a new ball if the

previous balls have not covered it. It is the centroid used to build ε -net in step one of Figure 3.11 based on a greedy algorithm or the Max-min method presented by Dłotko (2019). The output is a BM topological graph in step two of Figure 3.12, where each node corresponds to a ball, and edges connecting the nodes represent the intersections of these balls. Previous studies and experiments have demonstrated that as the value of the radius increases, the number of nodes decreases, resulting in a more connected graph, and vice versa. This relationship underscores the importance of the radius parameter in determining the structure and connectivity of the BM topological graph.

Figure 3.11 Toy P-shape point cloud used in illustrating the BM algorithm implementation and its output

3.3.5 Graph Invariant

Graph invariants help us to understand the structure and patterns of topological graphs or networks (Ren et al., 2023; Estrada, 2021). These invariants are crucial for analyzing complex networks, enabling researchers to understand the efficiency and resilience of networks or graphs across various fields, including chemistry, biology, computer science, and social sciences (Bogdan et al., 2021; Giannis and Guo, 2020). Some graph invariants considered in this work are the Estrada index, Graph density, number of cycle bases, fragmentation index, and node degree distribution.

Estrada index assesses the connectivity of a network by summing the exponential of the eigenvalues of the graph's adjacency matrix. The density of a graph measures the proportion of actual edges to possible edges, indicating how closely connected the graph is. The number of cycle basis counts the number of cycles or holes in a graph, providing insight into the graph's cyclic structure. The fragmentation index measures the number of connected components in a graph, reflecting its vulnerability, while the node degree distribution shows the pattern of connections among nodes, highlighting the network's connectivity and potential Central nodes (Ma et al., 2020; Bassett and Bullmore, 2016). In the following sections, we present the formulas for calculating these graph invariants, along with examples for illustration.

3.3.5 (a) Estrada Index

Estrada Index (EE): The Estrada index of an undirected graph G whose adjacency matrix has eigenvalues $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, \dots, \lambda_n$ is given as (Estrada and Higham, 2010):

$$EE(G) = \sum_{i=1}^n e^{\lambda_i} . \quad (4.1)$$

The Estrada index is a metric that captures the relative importance of a node within a graph. The simplest form of this centrality measure is the node degree, which represents the number of connections a node has with other nodes. It assesses the efficiency of a graph and indicates the extent to which each node participates in the subgraphs of the graph G .

Example 3.3

Given a topological graph $G = (N, E)$, where $N = \{n_1, n_2, n_3, n_4\}$ and $E = \{e_1, e_2\}$ as shown in Figure 3.13.

Figure 3.12 Toy topological graph G

Then the adjacency matrix A of the topological graph G is calculated as follows: where two nodes are connected, their adjacency or edge is 1; otherwise, the adjacency is zero if no edge connects the two nodes.

Solution

Table 3.4 Illustration of adjacency Table of Figure 3.12

	n_1	n_2	n_3	n_4
n_1	0	1	0	0
n_2	1	0	1	0
n_3	0	1	0	0
n_4	0	0	0	0

Therefore, the adjacency matrix is given as;

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix},$$

The eigenvalues can be obtained from the characteristic equation given by solving:

$$\det(AI - \lambda) = 0, \tag{4.2}$$

Solving the characteristic Equation (4.2) gives:

$$\lambda_1 = -1.414, \lambda_3 = 1.414 \text{ and } \lambda_4 = 0,$$

Therefore, from Equation (2.1):

$$EE(G) = \sum_{i=1}^4 e^{\lambda_i} = e^{(-1.414)} + e^0 + e^{(1.414)} + e^0, \quad (4.3)$$

$$EE(G) = 6.356.$$

The Estrada index provides insight into the connectivity and structural complexity of a topological graph or network.

3.3.5 (b) Graph Density

Graph density $D(G)$ of an undirected graph G with a node N and edges E is given as (Needham and Hodler, 2019):

$$D(G) = \frac{2|E|}{|N|(|N|-1)}. \quad (5.1)$$

where $|N|$ is the total number of nodes while $|E|$ is the total number of edges

The density helps to track the edge-to-edge ratio of G , where $\frac{|N|(|N|-1)}{2}$ is the maximum possible number of edges in an undirected graph, $0 \leq D \leq 1$, $D=0$. If the nodes in the graph do not have any edges, while $D=1$, if every node in the graph is connected to nodes with a unique edge.

Example 3.4

The density of the topological graph G Figure 3.12 is given as:

$$|N| = \{n_1, n_2, n_3, n_4\} = 4, \quad (5.1)$$

$$|E| = \{e_1, e_2\} = 2, \quad (5.2)$$

$$D = \frac{2(2)}{4(4-1)} = \frac{4}{12} = 0.3. \quad (5.4)$$

The density $D=0.3$ of the topological graph indicates that it contains 30% of the maximum possible edges it could theoretically have, given the number of nodes. This density level suggests that the graph exhibits a moderate degree of connectedness, with some nodes connected by edges, while a significant number remain unconnected.

3.3.5 (c) Number of Cycle Basis

This work will focus on the following structural indices of a topological graph, $G=(N,E)$.

Number of Cycle basis: The number or cardinality of the cycle basis of a graph G is the minimum number of cycles (*a connected graph in which every node has degree 2*) required to cover the entire cycle space of G . Considering G as a simplicial complex, the cardinality of the cycle basis is equivalent to the 1st Betti number β_1 of the complex, which is a topological invariant that represents the maximum number of holes that can be produced without separating the complex into distinct parts.

The number of cycle basis can be written as:

$$\beta_1 = |E| - |N| + CC. \quad (6.1)$$

where CC is the number of connected components of G

Example 3.5

The number of cycles basis of G in Figure 3.12, it is calculated as follows:

From Equations (5.2) and (5.3), the values of $|N|=4$, $|E|=2$ and $CC=2$ implies the number of connected components in G Figure 3.12.

Therefore,

$$\beta_1 = 2 - 4 + 2. \quad (6.2)$$

$\beta_1 = 0$ implies that there is no cyclic connected component in the topological G .

3.3.5 (d) Fragmentation Index

Fragmentation (CC): Considering graph G as a simplicial complex, the number of connected components or fragmentation can be expressed as:

$$CC = \beta_0. \quad (7.1)$$

where β_0 is 0^{th} Betti number. It answers the question of how many separate components the graph G has (Munch, 2017).

Fragmentation of G can be written in terms of β_1 following Equation (6.1) as:

$$\beta_0 = \beta_1 + |N| - |E|. \quad (7.2)$$

Example 3.6

From Equations (5.2), (5.3), and (6.2), the values of $|N|=4$, $|E|=2$, and $\beta_1=0$

Therefore, the Fragmentation index or number of connected components of G is given as:

$$CC = 0 + 4 - 2 = 2. \quad (7.3)$$

$CC = 2$, implies that the topological graph in Figure 3.12 has two connected components.

3.3.5 (e) Node Degree Distribution of Topological Graphs

The node degree distribution of topological graphs is typically visualized using histograms, which facilitate visual assessment and comparative studies. Let m be the number of nodes in a topological graph, where $h(k)$ is defined as the cardinality of nodes $n \in N$ of the graph G , such that the degree of n is denoted as $\delta(n)$ is equal to k . This categorizes nodes based on the number of edges or connections they have (Estrada and Higham, 2010; Van Steen, 2010);

$$h(k) = |\{n \in N : \delta(n) = k\}|, \quad (8.1)$$

while the sum of $h(k)$ is given as:

$$\sum_{k=0}^{m-1} h(k) = m. \quad (8.2)$$

$m = |N|$ is the cardinality or number of nodes in the graph. In the histogram, k is plotted on the x -axis as the node degree while $h(k)$ is on the y -axis as the frequency.

Example 3.7

Considering the topological graph in Figure 3.12, to determine the node degree distribution, the following steps are followed:

Table 3.5 Node degree of the topological graph in Figure 3.12

Nodes	Degree(k)	Freq. $h(k)$
n_1	1	2
n_2	2	1
n_3	1	2
n_4	0	1

Figure 3.13 Histogram of the node degree distribution of the topological graph in Figure 3.12

3.4 Summary

The methodology for achieving the three objectives of this thesis is presented and discussed in detail. To address the first objective, the study outlines the process of constructing topological graphs using the CM algorithm to capture pollutant behavior based on the shape of the data. A mathematical foundation is provided, including key topological concepts and the Nerve Theorem, which support the construction of graphs. The methodology involves dimensionality reduction using a filter function, followed by partitioning the data into overlapping intervals, applying a clustering algorithm, and constructing CM topological graphs that reveal complex relationships among pollutants.

For the second objective, the BM algorithm is introduced as an improved variant of the CM algorithm. BM uses a single parameter, the ball radius, to cover the dataset and form nodes based on data similarity. Connections between nodes are established when their corresponding balls intersect. Cosine similarity is used as the distance metric to measure similarity between data points, and the Max-Min algorithm is applied to select ball centres. This approach reduces reliance on multiple parameters while effectively capturing the underlying shape of the dataset.

Finally, to assess the performance of the CM and BM algorithms, some graph invariants are introduced and discussed, including the Estrada index, graph density, cycle basis count, fragmentation index, and node degree distribution. These metrics are applied to compare the structural properties and behavior of the resulting topological graphs.

CHAPTER 4

TOPOLOGICAL GRAPH REPRESENTATION OF AIR POLLUTANTS' BEHAVIOR USING CONVENTIONAL MAPPER AND BALL MAPPER ALGORITHMS

4.1 Introduction

This chapter presents results from applying the CM and BM algorithms to the simulated time series and air quality datasets discussed in Section 3.2. In this Chapter, Section 4.2 examines the impact of parameter values on the topological graphs generated by CM and BM and evaluates the feasibility of clustering time series with similar behaviors into the same node using simulated datasets from models such as AR, MA, ARMA, and ARIMA.

In Section 4.3, the CM algorithm is applied to the daily average concentration of PM_{10} datasets collected over a seven-year period (2012–2015 and 2018–2020) from 52 air quality monitoring stations in Malaysia. Clustered station time series are plotted to verify the CM topological graph's accuracy, and DTW is used to validate time series similarity, with results shown in a heatmap. The largest subgraph of each year's PM_{10} topological graph is further analyzed, with stations within the nodes plotted on a map of Malaysia to visualize geographical relationships in PM_{10} behavior across the regions.

Finally, in Sections 4.4 and 4.5, six datasets of daily concentrations of CO, NO_2 , $PM_{2.5}$, PM_{10} , O_3 , and SO_2 from 2018 to 2020 are analyzed using CM and BM algorithms. The results are evaluated to identify the most effective and efficient TDA technique for visualizing the dynamics of air pollutants. A comparative analysis of the CM and BM algorithms is conducted using graph invariants to evaluate the effectiveness of each method. In addition, the traditional HACA visualization is compared with the CM topological graph to assess improvements in interpretability.

4.2 Simulation

The feasibility and effectiveness of the proposed method are tested on a simulated time series dataset generated with models such as Autoregressive (AR), Moving Average (MA), Autoregressive Moving Average (ARMA), and Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) (Box et al., 2015). Table 4.1 presents the selected models for generating simulated stationary and non-stationary time series, as described by Alfian et al. (2017). This simulation experiment aims to evaluate the proposed technique capability to cluster time series based on their behavior. Seven different simulated stationary time series are obtained from each AR, MA, and ARMA model, whereas the other seven non-stationary time series are obtained from the ARIMA model.

For each model, 10 time series are simulated, each with 200 data points. Therefore, a total of 140 (that is, a total of 14 different models by 10 time series per model) simulated time series (each time series contains 200 points) are used to check the effectiveness of the CM and BM algorithms in clustering the data according to the behavior of the time series. Plots of stationary and non-stationary time series simulated based on AR (1) and ARIMA (1,1,1) models are shown in Figure 4.1 and Figure 4.2, respectively.

Table 4.1 The models used to simulate the stationary and non-stationary time series

No.	Stationary	No.	Non-Stationary
1.	AR (1)	8.	ARIMA (1, 1, 1)
2.	AR (2)	9.	ARIMA (1, 1, 0)
3.	MA (1)	10.	ARIMA (2, 1, 0)
4.	MA (2)	11.	ARIMA (0, 1, 1)
5.	ARMA (1, 1)	12.	ARIMA (0, 1, 2)
6.	ARMA (2, 1)	13.	ARIMA (2, 1, 1)
7.	ARMA (2, 2)	14.	ARIMA (2, 1, 2)

Figure 4.1 Example of a stationary simulated time series by AR (1)

Figure 4.2 Example of non-stationary simulated time series produced by ARIMA (1,1,1)

The Min-Max scaler is used in normalizing data to the range of $[0, 1]$. In the normalization method, the original data points X_i is transformed to $X_i^* \in [0,1]$, using the formula (Ali, 2022):

$$X_i^* = \frac{X_i - Min}{Max - Min}, \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n. \quad (9.1)$$

Min and Max are the minimum and maximum values of the data points X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n , respectively and X_i^* is the normalized value of the corresponding data points X_i . However, in PCA, standard normalization (Z-score standardization) is applied due to its sensitivity to the scale of the variables.

4.2.1 Implementation of the CM Algorithm on the Simulated Dataset

Before applying the CM technique to the simulated dataset, the following parameters were defined. PCA is used as the filter function, with five covers set at a 20% overlap percentage. HACA is chosen as the clustering tool, using Euclidean distance as the proximity measure, with two clusters and complete linkage to determine subsequent clusters. The CM technique is then applied to the normalized dataset, with the results shown in Figure 4.3. The figure illustrates that the simulated time series are categorized into stationary and non-stationary groups, demonstrating the effectiveness of the proposed method in distinguishing between these scenarios. Nodes are connected based on the similarity of their time series behavior, forming connected components that each comprise a similar simulated time series.

Figure 4.3 Topological graph of simulated time series with 5 covers and 20% overlaps produced from the CM application

Two singleton Nodes, S10 and S9, are apart from other connected components. These nodes comprise non-stationary time series simulated by ARIMA_1 and ARIMA_2, respectively, as shown in Figure 4.4. Further investigation revealed that these time series exhibit different behavior compared to the time series in the other two connected components of the simulated CM topological graph. The time series of ARIMA_1 and ARIMA_2, belonging to Nodes S10 and S9, respectively, are plotted together with the selected time series from the other two connected components labeled as Nodes S1, S2, and S6, which consist of simulated time

series of AR_1, AR_2, and ARIMA_3, respectively. The time series clustered in Nodes S10 and S9 exhibit distinct behaviors from the time series clustered in other nodes. This explains why the time series in the singleton nodes display trends that differ from those of Nodes S1, S2, and S6, which are part of the same connected component, as shown in Figure 4.3.

Figure 4.4 Plot of simulated time series clustered in Nodes S1, S2, S6, S9, and S10 of simulated CM topological graph

The application of CM for a simulation study involves experimenting with the topological graph behavior based on different parameters. This is because there are no optimal methods to determine the parameters of the CM algorithm (Larson et al., 2023), and the parameters are determined through experiments to find the value that yields an interpretable topological graph. Figure 4.5 illustrates the output CM topological graph structure as the parameters, including the overlap percentage, number of Covers, and number of clusters, are varied. A high overlapping percentage would cause the graphs to be highly connected, while a small number of Covers would lead to more distinct clusters, and vice versa. Despite variations in parameters, the distinctions between stationary and non-stationary time series, as depicted by the graph, are retained, highlighting the robustness of the approach in categorizing points based on their similarities.

Figure 4.5 Topological graphs of simulated time series by varying the parameters. (a) 5-Covers, 5% overlap, and the number of clusters is 2 (b) 5 Covers, 30% overlap and the number of clusters is 2 (c) 5 Covers, 50% overlap and the number of clusters is 2 (d) 5 Covers, 80% overlap and the number of clusters is 2 (e) 2 Covers, 30% overlap and the number of clusters is 4 (f) 4 Covers, 30% overlap and the number of clusters is 4 (g) 5 Covers, 30% overlap and the number of clusters is 4 and (h) 10 Covers, 30% overlap and the number of clusters is 4.

4.2.2 Implementation of the BM Algorithm on the Simulated Dataset

To construct a BM topological graph, the sole parameter required is the radius of the ball, which functions as the cover in this method. The BM technique is applied to the normalized simulated dataset, with $\varepsilon = 0.04$ resulting in the topological graph shown in Figure 4.6. This figure illustrates that the simulated time series are distinctly separated into stationary and non-stationary categories, highlighting the BM method's ability to distinguish between different time series behaviors.

Figure 4.6 Topological graph of simulated time series generated using the Ball Mapper (BM) algorithm.

Figure 4.7 displays the plot of the simulated time series clustered in Nodes 139, 125, 0, and 131 of the BM topological graph shown in Figure 4.6. Observing the figure, the behavior of the time series in Nodes 139 and 125 differs significantly from that of the others, which explains their status as singleton nodes unconnected to other nodes. In contrast, the patterns of Nodes 0 and 131, which belong to the same connected component, exhibit some similarities in their trend patterns. Additionally, the time series labeled Node 0_1 and Node 0_2, which are clustered within the same Node 0, display a substantial similarity in their trend patterns. This observation validates the accuracy of the BM algorithm in uncovering hidden behaviors within a dataset, demonstrating its ability to identify and cluster similar time series.

Figure 4.7 Simulated time series clustered within Nodes 0, 125, 131, and 139 of the Ball Mapper (BM) topological graph in Figure 4.6 with $\varepsilon = 0.04$.

Figures 4.8 and 4.9 illustrate the impact of varying the parameters ε on the structure of the BM topological graph with $\varepsilon = 0.003$ and $\varepsilon = 0.001$. When ε is set to a high value, the resulting graphs exhibit a high degree of connectivity, characterized by a smaller number of nodes, as the larger radius encompasses more data points within each ball, leading to fewer but more extensive clusters. Conversely, as the value is reduced, the graphs display a greater number of distinct nodes with reduced connectivity. This is because the smaller radius captures fewer data points within each ball, resulting in more localized and numerous clusters (Rudkin et al., 2023). These variations in the parameter demonstrate how it controls the granularity of the BM topological graph, affecting the balance between the number of nodes and the degree of their interconnectedness.

Figure 4.8 BM topological graph of simulated time series with $\varepsilon = 0.003$ produced from the BM algorithm

Figure 4.9 BM topological graph of simulated time series with $\varepsilon = 0.001$ produced from the BM algorithm

The simulation analysis demonstrates that adjusting the parameters may have a notable impact on the structure of the topological graph without compromising the data shape. This result is consistent across both the CM and BM algorithms, indicating that the underlying similarities in pollutant patterns are preserved despite variations in parameter configurations. Consequently, this flexibility enables analysts to tailor the parameter setup to suit their specific interpretive needs and context, making the analysis both robust and adaptable. Tunable parameters in the Mapper algorithm enable analysts to refine the clustering process, allowing the output topological graph structure to reflect domain-specific insights and hypotheses. This flexibility enhances the algorithm's effectiveness in real-world applications by allowing it to adapt to the unique characteristics of different datasets (Munch, 2017).

4.3 PM₁₀ Dataset for 2012 to 2015 and 2018 to 2020

PM₁₀ is a major contributor to air pollution and haze episodes in Malaysia, exhibiting significant spatial variability and distinct distribution patterns compared to other pollutants (Amran et al., 2015). Table 4.2 presents summary statistics for the yearly PM₁₀ dataset covering the period from 2012 to 2015 and 2018 to 2020. However, the 2016 and 2017 datasets were excluded from the analysis because they had over 20% missing data. Mean imputation was employed to handle the missing data below 20% in a dataset, following the approach outlined by Hadeed et al. (2020). This approach helps maintain the accuracy of the subsequent analysis. The comprehensive summary provided in Table 4.2 offers valuable insights into the summary statistics in PM₁₀ levels over the specified years, thereby enhancing the overall understanding of air quality statistics during these periods. This understanding is then used to implement the CM algorithm on the datasets, allowing for the analysis of the annual dynamic pattern of PM₁₀.

Table 4.2 Descriptive statistics of PM₁₀ daily average concentration for each year from 2012 to 2015 and 2018 to 2020

	2012 PM ₁₀ ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	2013 PM ₁₀ ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	2014 PM ₁₀ ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	2015 PM ₁₀ ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	2018 PM ₁₀ ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	2019 PM ₁₀ ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	2020 PM ₁₀ ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)
Mean	43	43	44	54	28	30	22
Median	40	39	38	45	25	26	19
Mode	33	33	32	42	26	22	17
Max.	396	581	448	380	180	238	476
Min.	9	1	1	1	5	4	5
1st Qu.	31	30	29	33	19	19	15
3rd Qu.	51	51	52	61	33	36	25

The CM is applied to the annual PM₁₀ dataset from 2012 to 2015 and 2018 to 2020, collected from 52 air quality monitoring stations, to compare the yearly behavior of PM₁₀ in Malaysia. In implementing the CM algorithm, PCA is utilized as the filter function, and HACA is used for clustering pullback data points (Behera et al., 2021). The clustering parameter for HACA is set to four, using the Euclidean metric for proximity measure and complete linkage for merging clusters. The percentage overlap is set at 30%, with five Covers for each year determined experimentally, following the approach of Guo and Banerjee (2017) and Derwae et al. (2023).

4.3.1 CM Topological Graph for 2012 PM₁₀

Before producing the CM topological graph, insightful results were obtained by examining the patterns of segments where the transformed dataset is partitioned into segments by 5 Covers. This partitioning process revealed the stations with the lowest and highest variability of PM₁₀ concentrations. Figure 4.10 illustrates the partitioned stations, with station index numbers detailed in Table 3.1, for each Cover, starting from Cover 0, Cover 1, to Cover 4, with a 30% overlap. In this figure, the x -axis represents the normalized factor loading PC1 of PM₁₀ concentration produced by the filter function PCA through the CM application, while the y -axis represents the corresponding station index.

Figure 4.10 Normalized Factor loading PC1 and partition of stations into 5 covers; Cover 0, 1, ..., 4, with 30% overlap for 2012 PM₁₀

HACA is applied to cluster the data points in Figure 4.10 based on proximity using the Euclidean metric. Each cluster is represented as a node, with edges connecting the nodes based on the percentage of overlap. The output is a CM topological graph, shown in Figure 4.11. In this graph, the highlighted node clusters seven monitoring stations: Perai, Tasek, Sungai Petani, Taiping, Kota Baru, Alor Setar, and Seri Manjung. These stations can be viewed by clicking on the nodes on the CM interactive interface. Additionally, this node is located in Cover 2, shown in Figure 4.10. In the CM graphs, nodes are labeled with alphanumeric codes as shown in Figure 4.12. The color of each node in the topological graphs represents different regions in Malaysia, and the node size corresponds to the number of air quality monitoring stations clustered within the node. The edges connecting the nodes in the topological graphs signify geographical connections between monitoring stations and their regions in Malaysia.

Figure 4.11 Graphical user interface displaying the topological graph generated using the Conventional Mapper (CM) algorithm through the KeplerMapper application.

Figure 4.12 presents a CM topological graph illustrating the behavior of PM_{10} pollutant across air quality monitoring stations in Malaysia for 2012. The nodes within the connected components indicate that air quality monitoring stations clustered in those nodes share hidden similarities in the behavior of PM_{10} concentrations they recorded in 2012. In contrast, singleton nodes represent stations that exhibited entirely different patterns of PM_{10} concentration. A table containing the content of each node is provided in Appendix Table A1. It can be observed that stations in the Northern and Central regions exhibited subtle similarities in their behavior, as reflected by the connectedness of Nodes A1, A2, A3, A4, and A5. Additionally, stations in Sabah showed subtle similarities with those in Sarawak, as evidenced by Nodes A10, A9, A8, and A7. Stations in the Eastern and Southern regions also exhibited similar behavior, as indicated by Nodes A14, A15, and A16. This visualization highlights the regional patterns in PM_{10} pollution and the levels of similarity in air quality among various areas in Malaysia. To confirm the similarity in behavior among stations clustered within a node, the time series of

some randomly selected nodes are subsequently plotted for comparison. This visual representation facilitates a clearer assessment of temporal patterns, yielding consistent results across the clustered stations.

Figure 4.12 2012 PM₁₀ CM topological graph with 5 Covers and 30% overlaps

To validate the effectiveness of the CM techniques in clustering stations with similar behaviors and linking nodes with subtle similarities, time series data from randomly selected nodes were plotted for verification. Figure 4.13 shows the average daily PM₁₀ concentration time series for stations clustered in Nodes A3, A5, A9, and A16. The trends indicate that the four air quality monitoring stations in Node A5 exhibit similar patterns, with an average concentration of 48.12 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Stations in Node A2 have an average concentration of 42.19 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, those in Node A9 have an average concentration of 37.11 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, and stations in Node A16 have an average concentration of 46.68 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. This algorithm efficiently clusters air quality monitoring stations with similar behaviors into the same nodes, as reflected by the trends in their time series. Additionally, DTW is employed to empirically verify the similarity of the time series of the stations clustered in the selected nodes, which are visualized through a heatmap, as shown in Figure 4.14. These findings are consistent across other years.

Figure 4.13 Time series plots of 2012 PM_{10} for monitoring stations clustered in Nodes A5, A3, A9, and A16 of the Conventional Mapper (CM) topological graph

To further verify the result in Figure 4.14, DTW is employed to assess the similarity between the time series of stations clustered in Nodes A2, A5, A9, and A16. Figure 4.14 presents a heatmap visualization of these similarities. The findings align with the topological graph, which connects Node A5 to Node A2, indicating similar PM_{10} behaviors recorded in the air quality monitoring stations clustered in these nodes for 2012. Similarly, the DTW analysis reveals that stations clustered in Nodes A9 and A16 exhibit distinct PM_{10} behavior patterns, as reflected in the topological graph. This consistency between DTW results and the CM topological graph reinforces the CM algorithm in clustering and connecting clusters based on the similarity in the behavior of the PM_{10} concentrations recorded. Having established the ability of the CM algorithm in capturing the behavior of PM_{10} between the air quality monitoring stations across the regions in Malaysia, the stations clustered in the most connected

component of the 2012 topological graph are plotted on the Malaysian map in Figure 4.15 for better visualization of the variability and geographical similarity of 2012 PM₁₀ concentration.

Figure 14 Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) heatmap that measures the similarity between the time series of air quality monitoring stations clustered in Nodes A5, A2, A9, and A16 of the 2012 PM₁₀ Conventional Mapper (CM) topological graph

Figure 4.15 is a map of Malaysia, illustrating the geographical distribution of selected monitoring stations, specifically highlighting those clustered within the most significant connected component of the topological graph depicted in Figure 4.11. This component, comprising Nodes A1, A2, A3, A4, and A5, reflects some similarities in the PM₁₀ concentration levels recorded in 2012. The stations within this connected cluster cut across the Northern, Central and Southern regions such as Petaling Jaya, Shah Alam, and Putrajaya, as well as other monitoring sites across different regions including Kuala Selangor, Banting, Batu Muda, Jerantut, Kota Bharu, Langkawi, Kangar, USM, Alor Setar, Tanjung Malim, Perai, Tasek, Sungai Petani, Taiping, Seri Manjung, and Seberang Jaya. The index numbers of the stations on the map correspond to those in Table 3.1.

Figure 4.15 Geographical locations of air quality monitoring stations clustered in the most connected Nodes (A1 through A5) of the 2012 topological graph

4.3.2 CM Topological Graph for 2013 PM₁₀

Figure 4.15 is the CM topological graph illustrating the behavior of PM₁₀ pollutants across air quality monitoring stations in Malaysia for 2013. A table containing the content of each node in the topological graph is provided in Appendix Table A2. The topological graph reveals that most stations in the Northern, Central, Southern, Sarawak, and Sabah regions exhibited subtle similarities in PM₁₀ behavior, as indicated by the strong connectedness of Nodes B1 through B9. Furthermore, stations in the Eastern region, represented by Nodes B15 and B16, also recorded similar PM₁₀ patterns. This connectedness highlights the regional similarities in air quality. However, a few stations showed distinct PM₁₀ behaviors, as they are represented by singleton or less connected nodes. This visualization highlights the regional patterns and homogeneous behavior of the PM₁₀ pollutant, as well as the general trends observed across different regions in Malaysia in 2013. The time series of stations clustered within randomly selected nodes are plotted in Figure 4.17 to visualize their trend patterns.

Figure 4.16 2013 PM₁₀ CM topological graph with 5 Covers and 30% overlaps

Figure 4.17 is the time series plot of air quality monitoring stations clustered in Nodes B1, B2, B8, and B11 with average PM₁₀ concentrations of 51.68 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, 48.52 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, 36.15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, and 33.91 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, respectively. The trends observed in the time series indicate that Nodes B1, B2, and B8 exhibit similar patterns in PM₁₀ concentrations despite variations in their average concentration. This trend similarity is consistent with the topological graph, where these three nodes are interconnected, suggesting a subtle relationship. In contrast, Node B11 shows a distinct trend, corresponding to its separation from the other nodes in the topological graph. This alignment between the time series trends and the topological graph highlights the topological graph ability to cluster stations with similar air quality patterns. Finally, the similarity in the behavior of the time series of stations clustered in a node of 2013 PM₁₀ topological graphs is further verified using DTW in Figure 4.18.

Figure 4.17 Time series plots of 2013 PM₁₀ for monitoring stations clustered in Nodes B1, B2, B11, and B8 of the CM topological graph.

Figure 4.18 presents a DTW heatmap, which measures the similarity between the PM₁₀ concentrations recorded at the stations clustered in Nodes B1, B2, B8, and B11, as shown in Figure 4.16. The results align with the topological graph, which connects Nodes B1, B2, and B8, suggesting subtle similarity in PM₁₀ behavior recorded in these air quality monitoring stations in 2013. Additionally, the DTW analysis in Figure 4.18 shows that stations clustered in Node B11 exhibit distinct PM₁₀ behavior, consistent with their separation in the topological graph. The stations that recorded similar PM₁₀ are visualized on the map in Figure 4.19 to further understand the geographical relationship in the behavior.

Figure 4.18 DTW heatmap measuring the similarity between the time series of stations clustered in nodes B1, B2, B8, and B11 of the 2013 PM₁₀ CM's topological graph

Figure 4.19 is a map of Malaysia, showing the geographical locations of the monitoring stations clustered within the largest connected component of the topological graph in Figure 4.16. This component, which includes Nodes B1 through B9, indicates a certain level of similarity in the PM₁₀ concentration levels recorded in 2013. The stations within these connected nodes are spread across Northern, Central, Eastern, Southern, Sarawak, and Sabah regions, comprising areas such as Bandaraya Melaka, Port Dickson, Kemaman, Balok Baru, Paka, Labuan, Keningau, ILP Miri, Perai, Tasek, Kuantan, Sri Aman, USM, Kapit, Seberang Jaya, Sungai Petani, Kuala Terengganu, Pegoh, Tanah Merah, Petaling Jaya, Shah Alam, Seri Manjung, Kota Bharu, Bintulu, Sarikei, Kota Kinabalu, Samarahan, Kuching, Sibul, Limbang, Seremban, Putrajaya, Cheras, Batu Muda, Tanjung Malim, Jerantut, and Taiping.

Figure 4.19 Geographical locations of air quality monitoring stations clustered in the most connected Nodes (B1 through B9) of the 2013 topological graph.

4.3.3 CM Topological Graph for 2014 PM₁₀

Figure 4.20 is the CM topological graph illustrating the behavior of PM₁₀ pollutants across air quality monitoring stations in Malaysia for 2014. A table containing the content of each node in the topological graph is provided in Appendix Table A3. The graph reveals that stations in the Central, Eastern, and Southern regions exhibit similar PM₁₀ behavior, as reflected by the strong connectivity between Nodes C1 through C6. Conversely, stations in the Northern, Sarawak, and Sabah regions demonstrate distinct PM₁₀ patterns, indicating regional differences. Overall, the weak connectivity observed in the 2014 topological graph suggests a lack of homogeneity in PM₁₀ behavior nationwide. Figure 4.21 presents time series data for stations clustered in Nodes C1, C3, C7, and C12, with average PM₁₀ concentrations ranging from 42.24 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ to 60.12 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. The trends reveal strong similarities between Nodes C1 and C3, indicating that they experience similar environmental conditions. In contrast, Node C12 exhibits a distinct pattern, consistent with its separation in the topological graph. Figure 4.22 further confirms these patterns through a heatmap generated from DTW analysis, reinforcing the substantial similarity between C1 and C3 and highlighting the diverse PM₁₀ behaviors at C7 and C12, consistent with the topological graph's structure. The station's most connected component is visualized through the Malaysian map.

Figure 4.20 2014 PM₁₀ CM topological graph with 5 Covers and 30% overlaps

Figure 4.21 Time series plots of 2014 PM₁₀ for monitoring stations clustered in Nodes C7, C3, C1, and C12 of CM topological graph

Figure 4.22 DTW heatmap measuring the similarity between the time series of stations clustered in Nodes C1, C3, C7, and C11 of the 2014 PM₁₀ CM’s topological graph.

Figure 4.23 shows a map of Malaysia, highlighting the geographical distribution of selected monitoring stations, with a focus on those clustered within the largest connected component of the topological graph presented in Figure 4.21. This component, which includes nodes C1, C2, C3, C4, C5, and C6, reflects a similarity in PM₁₀ concentration levels observed in 2014. The stations in this connected cluster are distributed across the Central, Eastern, and Southern regions, encompassing stations such as Jerantut, Kuantan, Kota Kinabalu, Limbang, Langkawi, Kangar, Kuala Terengganu, Tawau, Alor Setar, Labuan, Keningau, Sandakan, Tanah Merah, Bandaraya Melaka, Tanjung Malim, Muar, Bukit Rambai, Kuala Selangor, Petaling Jaya, Shah Alam, Seremban, Putrajaya, Cheras, Port Dickson, and Batu Muda.

Figure 4.23 Geographical locations of air quality monitoring stations clustered in the most connected Nodes C1 through C6 of the 2014 topological graph.

4.3.4 CM Topological Graph for 2015 PM₁₀

Figure 4.24 presents the CM topological graph showing the behavior of PM₁₀ pollutants across air quality monitoring stations in Malaysia for 2015. A table containing the content of each node in the topological graph is provided in Appendix Table A4. The graph reveals that most stations in the Northern, Central, Eastern, Southern, Sabah, and Sarawak regions exhibited a strong relationship and similarity in PM₁₀ concentrations, as indicated by the robust connectedness of Nodes D1 through D12. However, some stations in Sabah and a few other regions displayed distinct PM₁₀ behaviors, represented by singleton or less connected nodes. This topological graph indicates a generally homogeneous behavior in PM₁₀ concentrations recorded across most air quality monitoring stations in Malaysia for 2015, reflecting a consistent pattern of air quality in these regions during that year. Figure 4.25 further supports these findings by showing the time series plot for stations clustered in Nodes D1, D4, D7, and D15, with average PM₁₀ concentrations of 66.08 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, 54.26 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, 38.88 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, and 35.81 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, respectively. The time series trends reveal strong similarities in the behaviors of Nodes D1, D4, and D7, consistent with their connections in the topological graph. In contrast, Node D15 exhibits a distinct pattern, confirming its separation from the others in the topological graph. This finding is consistent with Figure 4.26, the DTW heatmap of the same nodes.

Figure 4.24 2015 PM₁₀ CM topological graph with 5 Covers and 30% overlaps for

Figure 4.25 Time series plots of 2015 PM₁₀ for monitoring stations clustered in Nodes D1, D4, D7, and D15 of CM topological graph

Figure 4.26 DTW heatmap measuring the similarity between the time series of stations clustered in nodes D1, D4, D7, and D15 of the 2015 PM₁₀ CM topological graph.

Figure 4.27 presents a map of Malaysia, depicting the geographical distribution of selected monitoring stations, with a focus on those clustered within the largest connected component of the topological graph shown in Figure 4.25. This component, which includes nodes D1 through D12, reflects a certain level of similarity in PM₁₀ concentration levels observed in 2015. The stations within this connected cluster are distributed across the Northern, Central, Eastern, Southern, Sarawak, and Sabah regions, encompassing stations such as Tawau, Kuantan, Paka, Sibul, Bintulu, Sarikei, Kuala Terengganu, Tanjung Malim, Kota Tinggi, Pasir Gudang, Kemaman, Jerantut, Balok Baru, Larkin, Bandaraya Melaka, Seremban, Cheras, Port Dickson, Nilai, Bukit Rambai, Seri Manjung, Muar, Kuala Selangor, Petaling Jaya, Shah Alam, Putrajaya, Batu Muda, Pegoh, Perai, Tasek, Taiping, USM, Alor Setar, Langkawi, Kangar, Seberang Jaya, and Sungai Petani.

Figure 4.27 Geographical locations of air quality monitoring stations clustered in the most connected Nodes D1 through D12 of the 2015 topological graph.

4.3.5 CM Topological Graph for 2018 PM₁₀

Figure 4.28 presents the CM topological graph illustrating the behavior of PM₁₀ pollutants across air quality monitoring stations in Malaysia for 2018. A table containing the content of each node in the topological graph is provided in Appendix Table A5. The graph reveals distinct PM₁₀ behaviors in stations in the Northern, Sarawak, and Sabah regions, as the isolated Nodes E5, E6, E10, and E15 show. In contrast, stations in the Eastern, Central, and Southern regions exhibit more similar PM₁₀ behavior, reflected in the connected Nodes E11 through E14 and E1 through E4. This contrast suggests that while some regions share common air quality patterns, others are affected by different factors, leading to variations in PM₁₀ levels. Overall, the 2018 PM₁₀ concentrations show weak connectivity across the country, indicating a lack of uniform pollutant behavior. Figure 4.29 provides the time series data for stations grouped in nodes E4, E8, E11, and E13, with average PM₁₀ concentrations of 27.9 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, 21.06 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, 24.18 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, and 29.15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, respectively. The trends reveal that Nodes E11 and E13 exhibit similar PM₁₀ patterns, consistent with their connection in the topological graph, indicating a subtle similarity in air quality for 2018. In contrast, Nodes E4 and E8 show distinct patterns, aligning with their disconnection in the topological graph.

Figure 4.28 2018 PM₁₀ CM topological graph with 5 Covers and 30% overlaps for

Figure 4.29 Time series plots of 2018 PM₁₀ for monitoring stations clustered in Nodes E4, E11, E8, and E13 of the topological graph

Figure 4.30 is a map of Malaysia that illustrates the geographical distribution of selected monitoring stations, with a focus on the monitoring stations clustered within the most connected component of the topological graph shown in Figure 4.28. This component, which includes Nodes E1, E2, E3, and E4, indicates similarities in PM₁₀ concentration levels recorded in 2018.

The stations within this connected cluster are distributed across the Northern, Central, and Southern regions, including Seberang Jaya, Perai, Kuala Selangor, Seri Manjung, Balok Baru, Bandaraya Melaka, and Kemaman.

Figure 4.30 Geographical locations of air quality monitoring stations clustered in the most connected Nodes E1 through E4 of the 2018 topological graph.

4.3.6 CM Topological Graph for 2019 PM₁₀

Figure 4.31 presents the CM topological graph for PM₁₀ concentrations in Malaysia for 2019. A table containing the content of each node in the topological graph is provided in Appendix Table A6. The graph reveals that some stations in the Northern region shared similar behavior with those in the Central region, as Nodes F1 through F3. Additionally, the Southern and Sarawak regions are represented by singleton nodes, indicating that they recorded different trends in PM₁₀ concentrations. Nodes F6 through F8 exhibit a subtle similarity in PM₁₀ behavior among stations located in the Eastern, Southern, and Sarawak regions. This topological graph indicates a non-homogeneous behavior of PM₁₀ pollutants across the country in 2019. Figure 4.32 and Figure 4.33 are the time series showing the trend of some stations clustered in a node or connected and the DTW heatmap of one the most connected components of Figure 4.31

Figure 4.31 2019 PM₁₀ CM topological graph with 5 Covers and 30% overlaps

Figure 4.32 Time series of stations clustered in Nodes F7, F3, F1, and F16 of 2019 PM₁₀ CM topological graph

Figure 4.33 DTW heatmap measuring the similarity between the time series of stations clustered in nodes F1, F2, and F3 of the 2019 PM₁₀ CM topological graph.

Figure 4.34 displays a map of Malaysia, illustrating the geographical distribution of selected monitoring stations, with a focus on those located within the largest connected component of the topological graph shown in Figure 4.32. This component, encompassing nodes F6, F7, and F8, represents a group of stations demonstrating similar PM₁₀ concentration levels in 2019. The stations within this connected cluster are spread across the Central, Eastern, and Southern regions, including Batu Pahat, Cheras, Kuala Selangor, and Manjung.

Figure 4.34 Geographical locations of air quality monitoring stations clustered in the most connected Nodes F6 through F8 of the 2019 topological graph

4.3.7 CM Topological Graph for 2020 PM₁₀

Figure 4.35 presents a CM topological graph illustrating PM₁₀ levels across air quality monitoring stations in Malaysia for 2020. A table containing the content of each node in the topological graph is provided in Appendix Table A7. The graph reveals strong similarities in PM₁₀ concentrations among stations in the Northern, Central, Eastern, Southern, and Sarawak regions, as indicated by the interconnected Nodes G1 through G10, suggesting a consistent PM₁₀ behavior across these regions. In contrast, stations in Sabah and a few other areas exhibit distinct PM₁₀ behaviors, represented by singleton or less connected nodes, suggesting significant differences in PM₁₀ levels compared to the more connected regions.

Overall, the graph indicates a generally homogeneous PM₁₀ pattern across most of Malaysia’s air quality stations for 2020, pointing to a consistent air quality trend in the majority of regions. Figure 4.36 presents time series plots for stations clustered within Nodes G6, G4, G1, and G12, with average PM₁₀ concentrations of 21.85 µg/m³, 18.99 µg/m³, 17.17 µg/m³, and 27.62 µg/m³, respectively. The time series reveals a similarity in PM₁₀ patterns among Nodes G1, G4, and G6, aligning with the topological graph, where these nodes are connected, indicating shared air quality behavior. However, Node G12 shows a distinct trend, reflecting its separation from the other nodes in the graph.

Figure 4.35 2020 PM₁₀ CM topological graph with 5 Covers and 30% overlaps for

Figure 4.36 Time series of stations clustered in Nodes G6, G4, G1, and G12 of 2020 PM₁₀ CM topological graph

Figure 4.37: Illustrates a map of Malaysia, highlighting the geographical distribution of selected monitoring stations, specifically those located within the largest connected component of the topological graph depicted in Figure 4.35. This component, which includes Nodes G1 through G10, demonstrates a level of similarity in PM₁₀ concentration levels recorded in 2020. The stations within this connected cluster are spread across the Northern, Central, Eastern, Southern, Sarawak, and Sabah regions, including stations such as Seberang Jaya, Taiping, Balik Pulau, USM, Perai, Alor Setar, Kulim, Sungai Petani, Balok Baru, Bukit Rambai, Cheras, Kuala Selangor, Larkin, Pasir, Pegoh, Putrajaya, Tasek, Kuala Terengganu, Manjung, Temerloh, Bandaraya Melaka, Kluang, Port Dickson, Segamat, Batu Muda, Indera Mahkota, Kangar, Kemaman, Kota Tinggi, Langkawi, Paka, Seremban, and Jerantut.

Figure 4.37 Geographical locations of air quality monitoring stations clustered in the most connected Nodes G1 through G10 of the 2020 topological graph.

4.3.8 Node Degree Distribution of Yearly PM₁₀ Topological Graphs

Figure 4.38 presents a node degree distribution histogram, a topological graph metric that summarizes and compares the structure of annual PM₁₀ topological graphs. This metric reveals the degree of connectivity in the graphs, reflecting inter-regional and intra-regional similarities in PM₁₀ concentrations. A higher node degree indicates stronger connectedness, suggesting that most stations recorded similar PM₁₀ levels across the region in that year. Conversely, a lower node degree indicates weaker connectivity, reflecting more substantial intra-regional similarities in PM₁₀ concentrations.

The histogram highlights years with notable connectedness, particularly 2013, 2015, and 2020, which exhibit higher node degrees. Specifically, the 2015 graph shows nodes with degrees of 4, 3, 1, and 0, while the 2020 and 2013 graphs display similar node degrees, indicating substantial inter-regional similarity in PM₁₀ levels. In contrast, 2019 demonstrates the weakest connectedness, with the highest number of degree 0 nodes, signifying limited inter-regional similarity. Moderately weak connectivity is observed in 2012, 2014, and 2018, with 2014 standing out slightly due to the presence of a degree 3 node, suggesting moderate inter- and intra-regional PM₁₀ similarities across some stations.

Figure 4.38 Node degree distribution of 2012, 2013, 2014, 2015, 2018, 2019, and 2020 PM₁₀ topological graphs

4.3.9 Comparison between Quantitative and Qualitative Analysis of PM₁₀ Behavior

A quantitative analysis of PM₁₀ concentrations is conducted using paired *t*-tests (Siegel, 2012) and corresponding *p*-values to detect significant year-to-year differences in the annual mean concentrations recorded at each of the 52 stations, as shown in Table 4.3. This analysis is compared with the results obtained from CM topological graphs. A Quantile-Quantile (Q-Q) plot confirmed that the datasets are approximately normally distributed, with a sample size of 52. The paired *t*-tests revealed significant differences in PM₁₀ concentrations for the following year pairs 2013 and 2015, 2013 and 2020, and between 2015 and 2020, all with $p < 0.05$. As highlighted in Table 4.3, these findings reveal notable discrepancies that contrast with the similarities observed in CM topological graphs across the same years. This is evident from the node degree distribution illustrated in Figure 4.38, a pattern also reported by Gillespie et al. (2024), who noted that quantitative methods do not analyze data based on their shape. While

this approach accurately quantifies the magnitude of changes in PM₁₀ concentrations, it provides limited insight into the shape of PM₁₀ data over the years.

Figure 4.39 presents a Spearman correlation heatmap illustrating the annual PM₁₀ concentration from 2012 to 2020 across various monitoring stations. The analysis reveals strong positive correlations between the years 2013 and 2015. However, these correlations weaken over more extended periods, particularly between 2013 and 2020 and between 2015 and 2020. In contrast, the qualitative topological analysis using the CM approach provides a broader perspective by examining the behavior of PM₁₀ based on the shape of the data. This approach identifies a level of similarity between 2013 and 2020, as well as between 2015 and 2020, in terms of variability and more substantial inter-regional PM₁₀ similarities, as shown in the topological graph. Unlike the quantitative method, the qualitative approach captures the shape of the PM₁₀ dataset, revealing relationships and behaviors that complement the statistical results but do not invalidate them; instead, it offers additional insights. These methods provide a comprehensive understanding of PM₁₀ behavior, combining quantitative and qualitative insights to highlight statistical differences and spatial trends.

Table 4.3 Yearly comparisons of PM₁₀ concentration mean differences with paired *t*-test

Year Pair	Mean Diff.	Std. dev	<i>t</i> -Value	<i>p</i> -Value
2012 vs 2013	0.274	5.133	-0.385	0.701
2013 vs 2014	0.226	7.936	-0.205	0.838
2013 vs 2015	9.598	7.582	-8.771	0.0001
2013 vs 2020	-22.031	11.919	12.672	0.0001
2014 vs 2015	8.707	5.513	-10.942	0.0001
2015 vs 2018	-26.216	14.164	11.409	0.0001
2015 vs 2020	-31.171	13.371	15.288	0.0001
2018 vs 2019	4.081	3.136	-7.915	0.0001
2019 vs 2020	-7.812	6.583	8.135	0.0001

Figure 4.39 Spearman correlation heatmap showing the relationships between annual PM₁₀ concentrations across all monitoring stations from 2012 to 2020

4.4 Comparative Analysis of CM and BM in Analyzing CO, NO₂, PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, O₃, and SO₂ Datasets for 2018 to 2020

Table 4.4 presents summary statistics for each pollutant dataset from 2018 to 2020. During this period, NO₂, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁₀ recorded maximum concentrations of 0.047 ppm, 407.154 µg/m³, and 475.965 µg/m³, respectively, values that exceeded the MAAQG on certain days, as shown in Table 3.3. Also, the number of monitoring stations varies across the pollutants because stations with over 20% missing values were excluded from the analysis to maintain data integrity (Kovtun and Fataliieva, 2020) while in the remaining stations, mean imputation was employed to handle the tolerated missing values, ensuring the accuracy of the analysis (Hadeed et al., 2020). The number of observations refers to the total count of records for each pollutant across all monitoring stations over the three years. Merging the three-year datasets

provides a more comprehensive view and could reveal the patterns and behaviors of the contaminants more effectively than a single-year dataset (Huning and AghaKouchak, 2020). This comprehensive summary enhances the understanding of the Central tendencies within the datasets.

Table 4.4 Descriptive statistics of CO, NO₂, PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, O₃, and SO₂ for 2018 to 2020

	CO (ppm)	NO ₂ (ppm)	PM _{2.5} (µg/m ³)	PM ₁₀ (µg/m ³)	O ₃ (ppm)	SO ₂ (ppm)
No. of Stations	46	52	59	53	45	48
No. of Observation	50,370	56,940	64,605	58,035	49,275	52,560
Mean	0.616	0.008	16.475	25.237	0.0175	0.001
Median	0.582	0.005	13.489	21.83	0.0162	0.0009
Mode	0.556	0.0035	9.553	26	0.0102	0.0008
Max	3.308	0.047	407.154	475.965	0.0621	0.0122
Min	0.08	0.0002	1.730	3.97	0.0002	0.0001
1 st Q	0.465	0.0033	9.097	16.241	0.0119	0.0007
3 rd Q	0.726	0.0085	20.028	29.9305	0.0218	0.0012

The TDA techniques, specifically the CM and BM algorithms, are applied to the dataset discussed and summarized in Table 4.4. Additionally, a comparative analysis of CM, BM, and HACA is conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of each approach in analyzing the air quality datasets. In the implementation of the CM algorithm, PCA is employed as a filter function, while HACA is used as the clustering method (Behera et al., 2021). The clustering parameter for HACA is set to 4, using the Euclidean metric for proximity measure and complete linkage for merging clusters based on similarity. The percentage overlap and the number of Covers or covers for each pollutant are determined experimentally. For the BM algorithm, the parameter is chosen through a series of experiments to find the value that generates a robust and interpretable BM topological graph for each dataset. These methodologies are applied to datasets comprising the concentration of NO₂, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, O₃, CO, and SO₂ from 2018 to 2020. The parameters for the CM and BM algorithms are further fine-tuned to yield CM and BM topological graphs with an equivalent number of nodes, ensuring an unbiased comparison

between the CM and BM topological graphs. The number of nodes is used as a control experiment to observe the node degree spread of each method (Bui et al., 2020; Kazikova et al., 2020).

4.4.1 CM and BM Topological Graphs of NO₂

Figures 4.40 and 4.41 present the topological graphs of the NO₂ dataset generated by the CM algorithm with 7 Covers and 30% overlap, and the BM algorithm with a radius $\varepsilon = 0.078$. In the CM graphs, nodes are labeled with alphanumeric characters, whereas in the BM topological graph, nodes are identified by numbers. The color of each node in both graphs represents different regions in Malaysia, and the node size corresponds to the number of air quality monitoring stations clustered within the node. The edges connecting the nodes in the topological graphs signify geographical connections between regions in Malaysia, as shown in Figure 3.2. This visualization offers a comprehensive view of the spatial distribution and clustering patterns of NO₂ concentrations across the air quality monitoring stations.

The analysis of NO₂ concentrations across Malaysian regions reveals varying patterns depending on the clustering and topological methods employed. Figure 4.40 is a CM topological graph that provides a qualitative representation of the NO₂ dataset. The graph highlights significant variations in NO₂ concentration levels among stations in certain regions for the entire 2018-2020 period. Notably, several stations in the Central region are clustered as singleton and disconnected nodes, suggesting distinct NO₂ behavior at these locations. In contrast, the connectedness between Nodes K1, K2, K3, and K4 reflects geographical relationships driven by similarities in NO₂ concentrations recorded at various stations across the Central, Southern, Northern, and Sabah regions. The CM graph also reveals connections between stations in Sarawak and those in the Central and Southern regions. To further investigate NO₂ patterns, the dataset is analyzed using the BM algorithm.

Figure 4.40 NO₂ CM topological graph with 7 Covers, 30% overlaps and 20 nodes

Figure 4.41 presents the BM topological graph, which displays a distinct clustering pattern, with the largest node comprising 18 air quality monitoring stations, predominantly located in the Central region, highlighting potential redundancy in air quality monitoring stations within this region. The BM algorithm reveals that several stations in the Southern, Northern, and Eastern regions recorded NO₂ concentrations comparable to those observed in the Central region, indicating the Central region as a significant hotspot for NO₂. The BM algorithm also identified stations in Sarawak, Sabah, and certain stations in the Northern, Eastern, and Southern regions as exhibiting unique behavior, clustering them into singleton nodes. This result contrasts with the CM algorithm, which clustered most stations in the Central region as disconnected components and connected Sarawak and Sabah stations with those in other regions. A detailed comparison of the CM and BM approaches is discussed in Section 4.4.1(a).

Figure 4.41 NO₂ BM topological graph with $\varepsilon = 0.078$ and 20 nodes

4.4.1(a) Comparison between CM and BM for NO₂

To compare the BM and CM methods, time series data from stations clustered in a randomly selected node of Figures 4.40 and 4.41 are plotted to observe and validate their trend similarities. Further analysis is conducted using DTW, with the results visualized through a heatmap, to confirm that stations within each node exhibit high similarity. In contrast, stations in connected nodes show some level of subtle similarities. Additionally, the efficiency and sensitivity of the CM and BM methods are compared by calculating the node degree distribution of their respective topological graphs, which is then presented as a histogram to identify the technique with a greater degree spread.

The CM algorithm clusters stations based on the similarity of pollutant variance explained in each station and in some cases similar amplitude of pollutant trends, as demonstrated in Node A1 of Figure 4.40, where stations with similar average NO₂ concentrations are clustered such as Balok Baru 0.005 ppm, Indera 0.005 ppm, Kota Bharu 0.004 ppm, Kuala Terengganu 0.004 ppm, and Kemaman 0.003 ppm, as depicted in the time

series shown in Figure 4.42(a). For the NO₂ CM topological graph. In contrast, Figure 4.42(b) shows the time series of stations clustered in Node 12 of Figure 4.41, revealing that stations in the Eastern and Central regions exhibit similar NO₂ trends, despite different average concentrations, and irrespective of the variance recorded among the stations. For instance, Seberang Jaya in Node 12 recorded an average NO₂ concentration of 0.013 ppm. At the same time, other stations in Node 12, such as Kuala Terengganu, Kota Bharu, Alor Setar, and Sungai Petani, have an average concentration of approximately 0.004 ppm, respectively. This highlights the BM algorithm ability to cluster or connect stations based on overall NO₂ trend patterns rather than the amplitude or variance of pollutant concentrations only.

Figure 4.42 Time series of stations clustered in: (a) Node 12 of the CM graph, and (b) Node A1 of the BM graph

Figure 4.43 illustrates the effectiveness of CM and BM techniques in clustering stations and connecting nodes with similar behavior. To assess the similarity of the time series shown in Figure 4.42 and validate the clustering results, DTW is applied to compare the time series data of the stations within the selected nodes. The DTW heatmap reveals a significant level of similarity among the stations clustered in Node 12 of the BM topological graph (Figure 4.41) and those in Node K2 of the CM topological graph (Figure 4.40). Notably, the BM algorithm successfully clusters Seberang Jaya with other stations in Node 12. However, as a result of ball intersection, it demonstrates a higher sensitivity in detecting similarities than the CM algorithm.

Furthermore, the BM topological graph connects Node 0, which contains the Shah Alam station, to Node 12, suggesting subtle similarities in NO₂ behavior between Shah Alam and the

stations clustered in Node 12, as validated by the DTW heatmap. The 95% confidence interval for the mean DTW distance between time series pairs of stations within the same or connected nodes in the CM and BM topological graphs lies between 0.0727 ppm and 0.1219 ppm, indicating a high level of similarity. This comparison highlights the BM algorithm ability to capture both local and global patterns in NO₂ behavior, providing a more holistic representation of the air quality dataset than the CM algorithm, which focuses on the variability in pollutant concentration due to the use of PCA as the filter function.

Figure 4.43 DTW heatmap measuring the similarities in the time series of randomly selected stations clustered in nodes of the CM and BM topological graph of NO₂.

Figure 4.44 compares the node degree distribution of NO₂ for CM and BM topological graphs, evaluating their effectiveness in clustering stations in a node and connecting nodes corresponding to stations with subtle similarities. The histogram of the node degree distribution of Figures 4.40 and 4.41 reveals that the BM topological graph has a greater node degree spread than the CM topological graph, suggesting that a greater number of stations across the regions exhibited similar NO₂ trend patterns rather than similar average NO₂ concentrations. This comparison highlights the BM algorithm ability to capture temporal and long-term patterns and trends of NO₂. In contrast, the CM algorithm emphasizes topological structure based on the

explained variance of the pollutants. The ideal topological graph produced by the CM and BM algorithms captures the underlying structure of pollutant behavior. This is reflected in the strength or weakness of node degrees, which indicate the complexity of pollutant interactions across monitoring stations. This could be based on domain knowledge of the pollutant; for example, gaseous pollutants are observed to be associated with higher node degrees, possibly due to their nonlinear and complex behavior.

Figure 4.44 Histogram comparing node degree distribution of BM with CM topological graphs of NO₂

4.4.2 CM and BM Topological Graph of PM₁₀

To further validate the effectiveness of the CM and BM algorithms in uncovering hidden behavioral patterns within air quality datasets, the CM algorithm is applied to the PM₁₀ dataset summarized in Table 4.4. Using four Covers with a 30% overlap, a CM topological graph is produced and presented in Figure 4.45. Notably, Node N11 is a cluster of stations in Sabah, which are interconnected with Node N10, a cluster of stations in the Northern region. This interconnection indicates that stations in Sabah exhibit PM₁₀ behavior similar to those in the Northern region. Node N12, a singleton node, also clustered six out of seven air quality monitoring stations in the Central region. Furthermore, Nodes N6, N7, and N8 reveal

similarities in PM₁₀ behavior among stations in the Northern, Eastern, and Southern regions, suggesting common factors or geographical proximity influencing PM₁₀ levels across these areas. Conversely, stations in Sarawak recorded the lowest average and distinct variance in PM₁₀ concentrations, forming singleton nodes and disconnected components, which highlights the different air quality dynamics in Sarawak compared to other regions. To gain further insights into PM₁₀ behavior, the BM algorithm is also applied to the dataset.

Figure 4.45 PM₁₀ CM topological graph with 4 Covers, 30% overlap, and 16 nodes

Figure 4.46 is a BM topological graph of PM₁₀ concentrations. The graph reveals that Node 0 predominantly clusters air quality monitoring stations from the Central region, which are interconnected with Nodes 16 and 17, representing stations from the Northern region, as well as Node 1, which connects Central region stations with Nodes 7 and 8, encompassing stations across the Eastern and Southern regions. This connectivity suggests that most stations in the Central region exhibit PM₁₀ behavior similar to that in the Southern, Northern, and Eastern regions. This pattern of PM₁₀ behavior, visualized through the BM topological graph, contrasts with the CM topological graph, where stations in the Central region form a singleton node, indicating that each method reveals a unique PM₁₀ behavior. Additionally, air quality monitoring stations in Sarawak exhibit distinct PM₁₀ behavior, forming separate clusters, whereas the two active stations in Sabah cluster in Node 29. Further investigation on the consistency of the CM and BM algorithms is conducted in Section 4.4.2(a).

Figure 4.46 PM_{10} BM topological graph with $\varepsilon = 0.062$ and 16 nodes

4.4.2(a) Comparison between BM and CM of PM_{10}

To validate the findings in Figures 4.45 and 4.46, time series data from stations in Node B1 of the CM topological graph and Node 36 of the BM topological graph were arbitrarily selected for further investigation. The time series of these stations were plotted to visualize trends, and the node degree distributions of the CM and BM topological graphs were calculated to compare the efficiency of the two methods. Figure 4.47(a) presents the time series plot of air quality monitoring stations in Sarikei, Sibul, and Samarahan, clustered in Node B1 of the CM topological graph in Figure 4.45, based on similar average and variability in PM_{10} concentrations. In contrast, Figure 4.47(b) displays the time series plot of stations Sarikei, Sibul, and Mukah in Node 36 of the BM topological graph in Figure 4.46, highlighting the sensitivity of BM to trend similarities. These findings consistently demonstrate that the CM algorithm focuses on average concentration values. In contrast, the BM algorithm emphasizes trends and dynamic behaviors over time, aligning with the results in the following discussion.

Figure 4.47 Time series of the stations clustered in (a) Node B1 of the CM topological graph and (b) Node 36 of the BM's topological graph.

To empirically assess the similarity of the time series of stations clustered within a node and the dissimilarity between stations in disconnected components, DTW is employed to measure the time series of stations in Nodes B1 and B5 of the CM topological graph, as well as Nodes 36 and 14 of the BM topological graph. The result is visualized using a heatmap, as shown in Figure 4.48(a). The DTW analysis heatmap validates the clustering outcomes of both the CM and BM algorithms by demonstrating that stations with similar PM_{10} levels are accurately clustered within the same node.

Notably, the Rompin station, exhibiting a distinct PM_{10} concentration and trend pattern, is isolated in singleton Node B5 in the CM topological graph and Node 14 in the BM topological graph, as shown in Figures 4.45 and 4.46, respectively, indicating a high degree of dissimilarity with other stations in the different nodes as shown in the heatmap. In addition, the 95% confidence interval for the mean DTW distance between station time series pairs in the DTW heatmap lies between $187.99 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and $409.38 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. This interval indicates a notable dissimilarity in PM_{10} concentration levels recorded at a station in a singleton node (Rompin in Node B5) compared to other stations (Mukah, Sarikei, and Sibul) in Nodes B1, B5 of CM and Node 36, Node 14 of BM topological graph of PM_{10} respectively. This finding aligns with the analysis of other pollutants examined in this study. Figure 4.48(b) shows the histogram of node degree distributions for both the CM and BM topological graphs, demonstrating that both

algorithms effectively capture comparable structural characteristics of the PM₁₀ dataset. This similarity is indicated by the closely aligned node degree distributions shown in the histogram.

Figure 4.48 (a) DTW heatmap measuring the similarities in the time series of randomly selected stations clustered in Nodes N1, N5, and Node 36, 14 of the CM and BM topological graphs of PM₁₀, respectively. (b) Histogram comparing node degree distribution of CM with BM topological graphs.

4.4.3 CM and BM Topological Graphs of PM_{2.5}

Figures 4.49 and 4.50 present the topological graphs of PM_{2.5} produced by the CM with 5 Covers and 20% overlap, BM algorithms with $\varepsilon = 0.065$, respectively. The CM graph reveals that stations in the Central region, as well as those in Sarawak and Sabah, exhibit distinct behaviors, clustered into disconnected components. In contrast, Northern, Southern, and Eastern stations show similar PM_{2.5} behavior, forming a connected component. The BM graph, however, indicates that stations in the Central region cluster in Node 0, reflecting similar trends in PM_{2.5}. It also suggests that most stations across Peninsular Malaysia share identical trends, indicating inter-regional geographical relationships in the behavior of PM_{2.5}. Finally, stations in Sarawak and Sabah demonstrate distinct PM_{2.5} patterns. To further verify the topological graphs, Figures 4.51(a) and 4.51(b) show the time series plots for stations in Node H2 and Node 20 of the CM and BM graphs, respectively. In contrast, Figure 4.51(c) provides a histogram of the node degree distribution, highlighting a close spread between the CM and BM graphs.

Figure 4.49 PM_{2.5} CM topological graph with 5 Covers, 20% overlap, and 20 nodes

Figure 4.50 PM_{2.5} BM topological graph with $\epsilon = 0.065$ and 19 nodes

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 4.51 Time series of the stations (a) clustered in Node H2 of the CM topological graph (b) clustered in Node 20 of the BM topological graph (c) Histogram comparing node degree distribution of BM with CM topological graphs

4.4.4 CM and BM Topological Graph of CO

Figures 4.52 and 4.53 are the topological graphs of CO produced by the CM with 7 Covers and 40% overlaps, BM algorithms with $\varepsilon = 0.048$ respectively. In contrast, the BM topological graph reveals substantial regional similarity in CO trend patterns, except in the southern region, where stations are clustered into distinct nodes. Figures 4.54 (a) and 4.54 (b) present time series plots for the stations clustered in Node M10 and Node 1 of the CM and BM topological graphs, respectively, illustrating that stations within these nodes exhibited similar CO behaviors. Additionally, Figure 4.54(c), a histogram of the node degree distribution, reveals that the BM topological graph has a greater node degree, suggesting that more stations recorded similar CO trend patterns than similar average and variance in pollutant concentrations across the regions.

Figure 4.52 CO CM topological graph with 7 Covers and 40% overlap and 20 nodes

Figure 4.53 CO BM topological graph with $\varepsilon = 0.048$ and 20 nodes

Figure 4.54 Time series of the stations clustered in (a) Node M7 of the CM topological graph (b) Node 1 of the BM topological graph (c) Histogram comparing node degree distribution of BM with CM graphs of CO

4.4.5 CM and BM Topological Graph of O₃

Figures 4.55 and 4.56 are topological graphs of O₃ generated using the CM with 5 Covers and 40% overlaps, and the BM algorithms $\varepsilon = 0.06$, respectively. In the CM topological graph, the connectedness of nodes within fragmented components highlights varying levels of regional similarity in O₃ behavior. Additionally, the BM topological graph equally reveals that O₃ exhibited consistent patterns across most stations in Malaysia's Northern, Central, Southern, Eastern, and Sarawak regions. However, certain stations, such as those in Sabah, displayed distinct behavior, as reflected by the connected nodes in the graph. Figures 4.57(a) and 4.57(b) illustrate the time series trends for stations in Node Q1 and Node 2 of the CM and BM topological graphs, respectively. Additionally, Figure 4.57(c) shows that the CM topological graphs exhibit slightly better node connectivity compared to the BM graphs, indicating that more stations recorded similar average and variance of O₃ concentrations across the region than similar trend patterns.

Figure 4.55 O₃ CM topological graph with 5 Covers and 40% overlap and 20 nodes

Figure 4.56 O₃ BM topological graph with $\varepsilon = 0.06$ and 22 nodes

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 4.57 Time series of the stations clustered in (a) Node G1 of the CM topological graph (b) Node 2 of the BM topological graph (c) Histogram comparing node degree distribution of BM with CM

4.4.6 CM and BM Topological Graph of SO₂

Figures 4.58 and 4.59 are the topological graphs of SO₂ produced by the CM with 7 Covers and 45% overlap, and the BM algorithm $\epsilon = 0.014$, respectively. Given the generally low SO₂ concentrations across monitoring stations, as shown in Table 4.4, most stations exhibited similar SO₂ patterns. However, the CM topological graph effectively captured this similarity in the average and variance of SO₂ concentrations, utilizing simple tree and cyclic node connections. In contrast, the BM graph, which heightened sensitivity, revealed similarities in SO₂ trend patterns, representing them as a complex network of nodes across all regions. Figures 4.60(a) and 4.60(b) show the time series trends for stations in Node L7 and Node 37 of CM and BM topological graphs and Figure 4.60(c) a histogram of the node degree distribution, indicates that the BM topological graph has a broader node degree spread, suggesting that more stations recorded similar SO₂ trend patterns than similar average and variance concentrations. Section 4.4.7 further compares the effectiveness of CM and BM topological graphs for the six air pollutants analyzed in this study using additional graph invariants.

Figure 4.58 SO₂ CM topological graph with 7 Covers and 45% overlap, and 23 nodes

Figure 4.59 SO₂ BM topological graph with $\varepsilon = 0.014$ and 22 nodes

Figure 4.60 Time series of the stations clustered in (a) Node L7 of the CM topological graph (b) Node 37 of the BM topological graph (c) Histogram comparing node degree distribution of BM with CM graphs of SO₂

4.5 Quantitative Analysis of CM and BM Topological Graphs for NO₂, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, O₃, CO, and SO₂ Using Graph invariants

The CM and BM algorithm parameters were fine-tuned to generate topological graphs with an equal and consistent number of nodes for each of the six pollutants, ensuring an unbiased comparison between the two methods in the quantitative analysis of their topological graphs. The number of nodes serves as a control variable, following the approach used by Bui et al. (2020), to observe the node degree distribution and evaluate connectedness, density, fragmentation, and the Estrada index as shown in Figure 4.61, which compared the graph invariants, highlighting the performance of CM and BM in representing pollutant behavior. Figure 4.61(a) shows the density of topological graphs for each pollutant, revealing that the BM algorithm produces denser graphs for SO₂, CO, and, to a lesser extent, NO₂. This indicates that the BM is more effective in capturing dataset dynamics compared to CM. Figure 4.61(b) presents the EE, which measures node efficiency and participation, showing relative similarity between BM and CM across pollutants, except for SO₂, where BM algorithm more effectively captures the pollutant underlying complex behavior by producing a topological graph that reflects its behavioral domain, with the graph variants reflecting its strong interactions across monitoring stations. Figure 4.61(c) illustrates the FI for both methods, demonstrating similar levels of graph fragmentation. Lastly, Figure 4.61(d) highlights the number of cycle basis in the topological graphs, indicating that BM is more sensitive to detecting cyclic behavior across the pollutants. Despite their differences, both CM and BM algorithms are invaluable for effectively simplifying complex air pollutant datasets, making them easier to visualize and interpret.

Figure 4.61 Graphs of the (a) density of BM and CM topological graphs (b) Estrada index (EE) of BM and CM topological graphs (c) Fragmentation index (FI) of BM and CM topological graphs (d) the number of cycle basis of BM and CM topological graphs

The computational time of the CM and BM algorithms in this analysis indicates that BM is faster across all stages. BM completes distance calculation, graph construction, and visualization in 0.006 seconds. In contrast, CM requires more processing time, with pre-processing taking 0.0040 seconds, lens generation taking 0.010 seconds, cover and clustering taking 0.007 seconds, and visualization taking 0.0929 seconds, resulting in a total of 0.1139 seconds. Table 4.5 summarizes further comparisons between CM and BM algorithms, highlighting the advantages and limitations of each technique.

Table 4.5 Advantages and Disadvantages of CM and BM Algorithms

No.	Features	Conventional Mapper	Ball Mapper
1	Parameter	Requires multiple parameters: filter function, cover of the filter range, and clustering algorithm.	It relies on a single parameter ε which is the radius of the balls.
2	Graph Construction Approach	A topological graph is constructed based on the preimages of data segments as defined by a filter function, covers, and a clustering algorithm.	A topological graph is constructed based on the balls built by greedy or Max-min algorithms ε -net.
3	Data Representation	Represents a dataset through a graph that captures structure influenced by the chosen filter function.	Represents a dataset through a graph that geometrically captures data points.
4	Ease of Interpretation	Interpretation is influenced by the choice of filter function, which can offer intuitive insights.	It can be more challenging to interpret due to the direct geometric approach.

5	Computational Complexity	It can be computationally expensive due to the need for clustering and handling complex filter functions.	Generally, it simplifies computation and is easy to implement.
6	Flexibility	Highly flexible in exploring data through various filter functions and clustering methods.	Less flexible in exploring data through different perspectives.

4.6 Comparison between TDA techniques and traditional HACA in Analyzing Air Pollutants Behavior

The dendrogram generated by the traditional HACA method is challenging to interpret because it fails to effectively separate clusters of stations with unique behavior as singletons, as noted by Ezugwu et al. (2020), Ran et al. (2022), and Huang et al. (2021). In contrast, CM and BM separate clusters with distinct behaviors, identifying them as singleton nodes, hence enhancing interpretability. While HACA follows a linear and hierarchical approach that lacks flexibility, CM and BM use a network representation to capture the relationships between nodes with some degree of similarity, offering more profound insights into the dataset.

The flexibility of TDA methods, such as CM and BM, allows for fine-tuning of parameters to adjust the output clusters. TDA methods can effectively represent high-dimensional datasets, providing better visualization and straightforward interpretation of complex patterns, making CM and BM more comprehensive and insightful tools for representing complex data. A simpler representation and visualization of geographical relationships in complex air quality datasets is achievable using topological graphs produced by the CM and BM algorithms than a traditional HACA.

Unlike the CM topological graph, where clusters are represented as distinct nodes that may connect to form components based on specific parameters, the HACA dendrogram relies on visual inspection to determine where to cut the tree and form clusters, which can complicate interpretation and understanding. With a large number of features or observations, the dendrogram can become cluttered and difficult to read, as each data point is represented by a

leaf node, making the diagram potentially overwhelming. By integrating HACA with CM, a more precise visualization of clusters can be achieved, providing a more transparent and more interpretable representation. These findings from the NO₂ dataset are consistent across the other pollutant datasets considered in this study.

Figure 4.62 NO₂ Dendrogram produced by traditional HACA

4.7 Summary

The result for Objective One is achieved by applying the CM algorithm to yearly PM₁₀ data to construct topological graphs that reveal the patterns of pollutant behavior. By leveraging PCA as a filter function, HACA for clustering and fixed coverage, with overlapping percentages across the years in the algorithm setup, the CM topological graphs revealed patterns in pollutant behavior. The findings highlight the algorithm effectiveness in clustering air quality monitoring stations according to the variance-driven dynamics of PM₁₀ across various regions. Additionally, the node degree distribution histogram is used to assess the similarity of PM₁₀ behavior across the years.

For the second objective, the BM algorithm is used to construct topological graphs for all the pollutants investigated in this thesis. The resulting BM topological graphs captured the dynamics of pollutants, reflecting both short-term variability and long-term trends of the pollutants across the stations.

Finally, the results for the third objective are presented using histograms to illustrate node degree distributions, and line plots to compare Estrada index, graph density, cycle basis, and fragmentation index for CM and BM topological graphs across the six analyzed pollutants. Additionally, the visualizations of the HACA dendrogram of pollutants are compared with the topological graphs to evaluate the clarity and interpretability of the clustering.

CHAPTER 5

DISCUSSION

5.1 Introduction

This chapter discusses the results presented and interpreted in Chapter 4 in the context of the thesis objectives. It focuses on how the TDA techniques, CM, and BM algorithms were applied to analyze the behavior of key air pollutants across Malaysia air quality monitoring stations from 2012 to 2015 and 2018 to 2020. The discussion interprets the findings in light of the study's goals, which include revealing the qualitative patterns of air pollutant behavior, identifying geographical relationships between monitoring stations, and evaluating the effectiveness of CM and BM algorithms in capturing complex pollutant dynamics. The results are analyzed based on how well the topological graphs revealed regional interconnectivity, temporal trends, and pollutant behavior, achieving the objective of providing deeper insights into air quality dynamics. Furthermore, this chapter evaluates the strengths and limitations of CM and BM algorithms, comparing their performance in visualizing spatial versus temporal pollutant patterns, and highlighting their potential for enhancing air quality monitoring and management practices in line with the study's aims.

5.2 Discussion of Results

The topological approach revealed that in 2012, the Northern region of Malaysia exhibited greater similarity in PM_{10} behavior compared to the Eastern and Central areas, likely due to transboundary pollution, particularly from large-scale biomass burning in Indonesia during the southwest monsoon. This transboundary haze can lead to regional similarities in PM_{10} concentrations as noted by Suris et al. (2022). However, the Southern region showed more similarity with Sabah and Sarawak despite their non-geographic proximity; this could be due to similar pollutant sources or other environmental factors. Geographic location, along with other factors, plays a pivotal role in shaping pollution patterns across different regions. This

relationship has been consistently supported by prior research, including studies by Qiao et al. (2018), Danek et al. (2022), and Guo et al. (2022), which utilized Geographic Information System (GIS) tools. Topological analysis of air pollutants further highlights significant geographical and temporal patterns, demonstrating how similar pollution sources can affect distinct regions. These findings offer a robust framework for understanding and interpreting pollution behavior across Malaysia, emphasizing the regional interconnectivity of pollutant dynamics.

In 2013, Malaysia experienced severe haze conditions, resulting in a significant increase in PM₁₀ levels, particularly in Peninsular Malaysia (Latif et al., 2018). The topological graphs revealed that stations in Southern Malaysia became more similar to those in the Northern, Central, and Eastern regions, reflecting the widespread impact of haze, which agrees with the findings of Samsuddin et al. (2018). This resulted in a high level of interconnectivity between stations in these regions, driven by the substantial increase in PM₁₀ concentrations. However, stations in Sabah and Sarawak were less affected, recording lower pollution levels. These findings align with previous research by Zulkepli et al. (2022) that identified the Central and Southern regions as the most severely impacted areas during the haze, with PM₁₀ concentrations reaching critical levels. The topological analysis effectively captures the temporal changes in pollutant behavior, illustrating the geographical spread and intensity of haze impact across the nation.

In subsequent years, the behavior of air pollutants continued to fluctuate. The year 2014 saw a decline in PM₁₀ concentrations compared to 2013, resulting in less connectivity between regions in the topological graphs. In 2015, another severe haze episode occurred, resulting in a significant resurgence of PM₁₀ levels, particularly in the Central and Southern regions. The topological graphs from these years differentiate heavily polluted areas from those less affected, with regions like Sabah and Sarawak maintaining lower pollution levels. These findings are

consistent with those of Khir et al. (2018) and Sentian et al. (2019), which reinforce the understanding of how both regional geography and environmental factors, such as haze, influence fluctuations in air pollutant behavior. The topological graphs offer a comprehensive visualization of these trends, providing valuable insights into interpreting regional similarities in air pollution dynamics.

However, by 2018 and 2019, the TDA revealed distinct PM₁₀ behaviors across various regions, with stations in the Northern, Sarawak, and Sabah regions showing isolated clusters, while stations in the Eastern, Central, and Southern areas exhibited more interconnected clusters. This suggests regional variations in pollutant behavior, driven by different local environmental or geographical factors. In 2020, however, a substantial homogeneity in PM₁₀ concentrations was observed across most regions, including the Northern, Central, Eastern, Southern, and Sarawak regions. This uniformity was likely influenced by the COVID-19 pandemic and the associated Movement Control Order (MCO), which resulted in a significant reduction in industrial and vehicular activities (Latif et al., 2021; Farahiyah et al., 2022). In contrast, some stations in Sabah and a few other regions showed distinct pollutant behaviors, suggesting localized sources of pollution. Overall, the 2020 topological graph reflects a more consistent air quality trend across the majority of areas, likely driven by reduced human activity during the pandemic. Lastly, the PM₁₀ behavior in 2013, 2015, and 2020 showed a high level of similarity, as reflected by the strong connectedness of their topological graphs.

Furthermore, the analysis of NO₂, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, O₃, CO, and SO₂ concentrations using CM and BM algorithms revealed distinct clustering and behavioral patterns across Malaysia's regions. For NO₂, the CM algorithm highlighted distinct behaviors, particularly in the Central region, where stations were often isolated due to their high concentration levels, likely from industrial and urban sources (Mohtar et al., 2018). Meanwhile, the BM algorithm identified broader similarities in NO₂ trends across regions, clustering stations with similar temporal

patterns, even if their average and variance concentrations differed. This showed the BM's ability to detect local and global behavioral similarity, whereas the CM focused more on spatial relationships based on variance in concentrations (Yang et al., 2019; Vîrghileanu et al., 2020). For PM₁₀, both algorithms displayed similar results, with Central region stations forming major clusters. However, the BM approach offered deeper insights by showing connections across regions, suggesting shared influences like the monsoon, traffic emissions, or transboundary haze, which impact PM₁₀ levels in the various areas, including the Southern, Northern, and Eastern regions which is consistent with studies done by Chang et al. (2018), Khan et al. (2020), and Othman et al. (2021).

For pollutants such as PM_{2.5}, O₃, CO, and SO₂, the results followed a similar pattern, where the CM algorithm effectively identified spatial similarities based on average and variance in concentrations, while the BM algorithm excelled in revealing underlying temporal trends. For example, the BM topological graph demonstrated notable consistency in PM_{2.5} behavior across Peninsular Malaysia, with only the stations in Sarawak and Sabah showing distinct trends, as also observed by Shaziyani et al. (2020). For O₃ and CO, both algorithms reflected regional similarities. Still, BM was more sensitive to subtle changes in the trend patterns, particularly in regions affected by seasonal events, such as the Southeast Asian haze or the MCO during the COVID-19 pandemic, which significantly reduced CO levels across urban and industrial areas (Latif et al., 2021; Farahiyah et al., 2022). SO₂, with its generally low concentrations, displayed strong regional similarities in both algorithms; however, the BM approach captured more complex interactions and subtle trend similarities across the regions, similar to the finding of Baidrulhisham et al. (2022). Overall, the combination of CM and BM algorithms provided a comprehensive understanding of pollutant behaviors, with CM focusing on spatial relationships and BM revealing temporal patterns.

Finally, the CM and BM algorithms offer distinct yet complementary approaches to air quality analysis. The CM clustering stations are based on average and variability in pollutant concentrations to reveal spatial relationships. At the same time, the BM focuses on overall trend patterns, identifying temporal similarities even when average or variance concentrations differ. BM is particularly effective in capturing local and global pollutant behavior and subtle temporal trends that CM may overlook. A comparison of node degree distributions highlights BM's ability to capture a broader range of pollutant behaviors, whereas CM focuses more on spatial relationships tied to average values. The combined spatial focus of CM and temporal sensitivity of BM offers a more comprehensive understanding of air quality dynamics, enhancing the interpretation of complex pollutant datasets.

Unlike the traditional HACA method, which connects all clusters without effectively separating unique behaviors, CM and BM separate distinct clusters as singleton nodes, improving interpretability. The flexibility of these TDA methods enables fine-tuning to represent high-dimensional datasets better, providing clearer visualization and interpretation of complex patterns. This advantage is consistent across various pollutants, demonstrating that CM and BM give a more straightforward and effective visualization of geographical relationships compared to traditional methods, such as HACA.

5.3 Significance of Quantitative Analysis of CM and BM Topological Graphs Using Graph Invariants

The quantitative analysis of CM and BM topological graphs using graph invariants is essential for evaluating their effectiveness in representing complex data structures. Metrics such as node degree distribution, fragmentation index, graph density, and the Estrada index provide measurable insights into the connectivity and structure of these graphs. Node degree distribution highlights variations in connectivity, enabling the identification of key regions or pollutants with similar concentration behaviors. The fragmentation index measures the degree of graph disconnection, providing insights into the heterogeneous behaviors of pollutants.

Graph density reflects the overall connectivity level, with higher values indicating a more interrelated behavior among pollutants. The Estrada index offers a global perspective on connectivity, indicating the degree of cohesion within the pollutant network.

Comparing these metrics between CM and BM, as shown in Figure 4.61, the BM algorithm captures pollutant interactions and behaviors more effectively than the CM algorithm. Differences in graph density and node degree distribution reveal how well each method represents localized versus global pollutant behaviors. A fragmented graph indicates isolated regional patterns, while a high Estrada index suggests strong overall network connectivity. These metrics collectively enable a robust quantitative assessment of the algorithms ability to represent the structure and dynamics of air pollutant data. Overall, the BM outperformed CM in capturing the general behavior of the pollutants using the graph metrics.

5.4 Advantages of Topological Clustering for Pollution Analysis and Control

The results obtained from applying CM and BM to the pollutant data highlight distinct advantages in capturing patterns often missed by traditional HAC. CM, through its use of a filter function, discriminates the characteristics of the data, such as average and variance in pollutant concentrations, effectively clustering stations with similar average or variance concentrations of pollutants into the same node. Stations that recorded slightly different but close variances were clustered in connected nodes, reflecting hidden variations. Singleton nodes represent stations with unique pollutant concentrations. This approach allowed CM to identify similarities in variability in pollutant concentrations, whether increasing, decreasing, or stable across the entire monitoring period. CM was less sensitive to detecting short-term anomalies, as its primary focus was on uncovering broader, long-term patterns and similarities in pollutant variability across stations.

BM offered a complementary perspective, excelling in detecting similarity in both short-term fluctuations and long-term trends in pollutant levels. Its geometric approach enabled

the identification of similarities between stations that experienced sudden changes or anomalies, which CM often overlooked. This capability proved particularly valuable for detecting transient pollution spikes, which can signify critical environmental events. Additionally, BM's topological framework captured the global structure of the data, revealing similarities in long-term and recurring pollution patterns over specific intervals, providing a clearer understanding of the pollutants' overall behavior.

Topological clustering, compared to traditional clustering methods, proved to be an effective data visualization tool that provides better insights into the dataset than traditional HACA. From the CM and BM topological graphs in Figures 4.40 and 4.41, the dataset's visualization appears well-organized, with all nodes differentiated by cluster membership. In contrast, the results from traditional HACA in Figure 4.62 show only three major clusters, making it difficult to interpret the dendrograms and easily detect which subclusters each station belongs to. Unlike HACA, which creates rigid, non-overlapping clusters based purely on distance metrics applied directly to the dataset, CM and BM produced flexible structures that can be fine-tuned through parameter adjustment to obtain more refined clusters and connect clusters with relatively similar pollutant behaviors. This flexibility revealed connections that rigid HACA boundaries often overlooked, while a case where several stations clustered within the same node highlighted possible redundancies in monitoring stations, offering opportunities for optimizing air quality monitoring.

The findings suggest that the application of topological clustering in pollution control could support environmental policy initiatives by facilitating collaboration among stations within clustered nodes. Through centralized pollution control methodologies, emissions from various sources within these nodes might be reduced more effectively. Community members residing within the stations clustered in a node and connected nodes may collaborate on pollution control measures aligned with government policies, potentially implementing

coordinated plans for emission reduction, synchronized operations, and joint efforts to transition to cleaner processes. This approach may enable effective control measures as communities share successful techniques, and compensation strategies for environmental impact can be developed in collaboration with local stakeholders (Arora et al., 2020).

5.5 Study Limitations

Despite the demonstrated strengths of the CM and BM algorithms in this study, several limitations persist. The CM algorithm, in particular, relies on multiple sensitive parameters, including the filter function, cover configuration, overlap percentage, and clustering method. Due to the lack of a standardized procedure for optimal parameter selection, there is currently no established method for selecting optimal parameters, resulting in a reliance on manual tuning approaches. This reliance can introduce variability and affect the stability of the resulting topological graphs.

Although the BM algorithm simplifies the topological graph construction process by depending on a single parameter, the ball radius, however, this simplicity comes with a limitation, such as the risk of oversimplification, which can lead to the loss of essential information inherent in the dataset. Given the lack of an optimal approach for determining the most suitable parameter value, this limitation may compromise the accuracy and reliability of the resulting topological graph representation.

For comparative analysis of CM and BM algorithms, the graph invariants such as the Estrada index, graph density, cycle basis, fragmentation index, and node degree distribution offer valuable insights for comparing CM and BM graph structures; however, the evaluation remains descriptive mainly as they are solely depending on the topological graph structure. Currently, there is no standardized statistical framework to quantitatively assess the significance of structural differences between the outputs of CM, BM, and HACA. This limits the extent to which rigorous comparative conclusions can be drawn.

CHAPTER 6

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

6.1 Conclusion

Air pollution continues to pose a significant global threat to environmental and public health, particularly in rapidly urbanizing and industrializing regions such as Malaysia. Understanding pollutant behavior across geographically diverse areas is challenging, especially given the high dimensionality and large volume of data collected from multiple monitoring stations. Traditional quantitative techniques often struggle to capture hidden patterns, overlapping clusters, or topological relationships among stations. This thesis presents an alternative approach using qualitative topological data analysis (TDA) tools, namely the conventional Mapper (CM) and its variant, the Ball Mapper (BM), which can uncover hidden structures and provide insights into pollutant behavior based on the shape of the data.

The CM algorithm is used to generate topological graphs representing the yearly behavior of PM_{10} from 2012 to 2015 and from 2018 to 2020. These topological graphs revealed relationships among monitoring stations, with notable similarities in PM_{10} behavior observed in 2013, 2015, and 2020. Nodes and edges in the CM topological graphs illustrated clusters of stations exhibiting similar pollutant behavior, which were further validated using Dynamic Time Warping.

Furthermore, the BM algorithm is applied to analyze six pollutants, including NO_2 , PM_{10} , $PM_{2.5}$, O_3 , CO , and SO_2 , using data from 2018 to 2020. The topological graphs produced by the BM algorithm captured both short-term variations and long-term trends in pollutant behavior. This method provided a simple yet effective visualization, and the algorithm appeared to perform slightly better in representing the behavior of some pollutants, such as O_3 , CO , and SO_2 .

Also, a comparative evaluation of the CM and BM algorithms in representing pollutant behavior is conducted using topological graph invariants such as graph density, fragmentation index, and the Estrada index. The BM algorithm consistently produced denser, more interconnected graphs with richer cyclic structures, indicating strong sensitivity to temporal trends. In contrast, CM is more effective in highlighting spatial variance due to its filter function. However, while informative, it relies on visual inspection of the dendrogram to determine where to cut the tree to form clusters, which can complicate interpretation. In comparison, topological graphs represent clusters as distinct nodes that may connect to form components.

In conclusion, this thesis successfully achieved its objectives by introducing and applying the CM and BM algorithms to air quality analysis. The resulting topological graphs offered novel insights into pollutant behavior, capturing the dynamic relationships in pollutant patterns across monitoring stations based on data shape. These findings highlight qualitative topological data analysis methods as a valuable complement to traditional statistical approaches, with potential applications in optimizing air quality monitoring networks and shaping data-driven environmental policies.

6.2 Future Work

To address the manual parameter selection approach in the CM algorithm, future research should focus on developing automated or data-driven methods for parameter selection. Techniques such as optimization heuristics or Bayesian optimization (Banchhor and Srinivasu, 2021) could be explored to identify optimal values for the filter function, the number of covers, the overlap percentage, and the clustering method. This would help reduce subjectivity, improve reproducibility, and enhance the robustness of the resulting topological graphs.

However, in the case of the BM algorithm, further work could focus on establishing a systematic strategy for selecting the ball radius parameter beyond scaling methods and stability-

based selection criteria. This may include integration with supervised machine learning techniques, such as decision trees, random forests, or neural networks, to predict performance cluster purity and topological stability based on different radius values. Such enhancements would reduce the risk of oversimplification and improve the ability of BM to preserve essential structural information within the dataset.

Lastly, for a comparative analysis of CM and BM algorithms, future studies should aim to establish a formal statistical framework for evaluating and comparing topological graph structures. This includes designing hypothesis-driven statistical tests to assess the significance of differences between CM, BM, and HACA outputs, beyond qualitative or descriptive graph invariants. Incorporating statistical validation would enable more rigorous, interpretable, and generalizable conclusions in topological data analysis applied to air quality data.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A

Tables containing the stations clustered in the nodes of the conventional Mapper topological graphs in Figures 4.12, Appendix A1, Figure 4.16, Appendix A2, Figure 4.20, Appendix A3, Figure 4.24, Appendix A4, Figure 4.28, Appendix A5, Figure 4.31, Appendix A6, and Figure 4.35, Appendix A7.

Appendix Table A1

Node ID	Stations Clustered
A1	Petaling_Jaya,Shah_Alam,Kuala_Selangor,Banting
A2	Kuala_Selangor, Putrajaya, Batu_Muda
A3	Jerantut,Langkawi,Kangar,USM,Alor_Setar,Tanjung_Malim, Putrajaya
A4	Perai,Tasek,Sungai_Petani,Taiping,Kota_Bharu,Alor_Setar,Seri_Manjung
A5	Seberang_Jaya,Sungai_Petani
A6	ILP_Miri
A7	Kuantan,Larkin,Paka,Kota_Kinabalu,Tawau
A8	Paka,Miri,Kota_Kinabalu,Limbang,Tawau,Labuan,Keningau,Sandakan
A9	Bintulu,Miri,Labuan,Kapit
A10	Kapit
A11	Pasir_Gudang,Kemaman
A12	Pasir_Gudang,Samarahan,Kota_Tinggi
A13	Kuching,Sarikei,Samarahan
A14	Tanah_Merah
A15	Kuala_Terengganu,Pegoh,Port_Dickson,Tanah_Merah
A16	Balok_Baru,Kuala_Terengganu,Bandaraya_Melaka,MuarSeremban,Port_Dickson
A17	Nilai, Cheras
A18	Bukit_Rambai
A19	Sibu, Sri_Aman
A20	Klang

Appendix Table A2

Node ID	Stations Clustered
B1	Bandaraya_Melaka,Port_Dickson
B2	Kemaman,Balok_Baru,Port_Dickson
B3	Klang
B4	Paka,Labuan,Keningau,ILP_Miri
B5	Perai,Kuching,Tasek,Kota_Bharu,Sibu,Bintulu,Miri,Sarikei,Kota_Kinabalu,Limbang,USM,Kapit
B6	Seberang_Jaya,Sungai_Petani,Kuala_Terengganu,USM,Pegoh,Tanah_Merah
B7	Petaling_Jaya,Shah_Alam,Pegoh,Seremban,Putrajaya,Cheras,Batu_Muda
A8	Seri_Manjung,Tanjung_Malim,Kuala_Selangor,Putrajaya,Cheras,Batu_Muda
B9	Jerantut,Taiping,Tanjung_Malim
B10	Kapit
B11	Langkawi,Kangar,Tawau,Alor_Setar,Sandakan
B12	Pasir_Gudang,Larkin,Kota_Tinggi
B13	Larkin
B14	Muar
B15	Nilai, Banting
B16	Nilai

Appendix Table A3

Node ID	Stations Clustered
C1	Bukit_Rambai,Bandaraya_Melaka,Muar
C2	Kangar, Alor_Setar,Bandaraya_Melaka,Muar,Tanjung_Malim,Tanah_Merah
C3	Jerantut, Kuantan,Kota_Kinabalu,Limbang,Langkawi,Kangar,Kuala_Terengganu, Tawau,Alor_Setar,Labuan, Keningau,Sandakan, Tanah_Merah
C4	Petaling_Jaya,Shah_Alam,Tanjung_Malim,Seremban Kuala_Selangor,Putrajaya,Cheras,Port_Dickson,Batu_Muda
C5	Petaling_Jaya,Shah_Alam,Batu_Muda
C6	Kuala_Selangor
C7	Perai,Tasek,Seberang_Jaya,Taiping,USM,Seri_Manjung,Pegoh
C8	Tasek,Seberang_Jaya,Taiping,Seri_Manjung,Pegoh
C9	Sungai_Petani
C10	Kuching,Bintulu,Miri,Sarikei,Samarahan,Kapit,ILP_Miri
C11	Sibu,Samarahan,Sri_Aman
C12	Paka
C13	Pasir_Gudang,Kemaman,Balok_Baru,Larkin
C14	Larkin,Kota_Bharu,Kota_Tinggi
C15	Banting
C16	Nilai

Appendix Table A4

Node ID	Stations Clustered
D1	Seberang_Jaya,Sungai_Petani,USM
D2	Perai,Tasek,Taiping,USM,Alor_Setar,Seri_Manjung,Pegoh
D3	Perai,Langkawi,Kangar
D4	Seri_Manjung,Pegoh,Kuala_Selangor
D5	Pasir_Gudang,Kemaman,Jerantut,Kuantan,Balok_Baru,Larkin,Paka, Kuala_Terengganu,Muar,Kuala_Selangor
D6	Kuantan,Paka,Sibu,Bintulu,Sarikei,Kuala_Terengganu,Tawau, Tanjung_Malim,Kota_Tinggi
D7	Tawau
D8	Pasir_Gudang,Kemaman
D9	Petaling_Jaya,Shah_Alam,Putrajaya,Batu_Muda
D10	Petaling_Jaya,Bandaraya_Melaka,Muar,Seremban,Putrajaya,Cheras, Port_Dickson,Batu_Muda
D11	Bukit_Rambai,Bandaraya_Melaka,Port_Dickson
D12	Nilai, Seremban
D13	Kuching,Samarahan,Sri_Aman
D14	Kuching,Sri_Aman
D15	Miri,Kota_Kinabalu,Limbang,Labuan,Keningau,Sandakan
D16	Kota_Bharu,Tanah_Merah
D17	Kota_Bharu
D18	ILP_Miri
D19	KlangBanting
D20	Kapit

Appendix Table A5

Node ID	Stations Clustered
E1	Balok_Baru,Bandaraya_Melaka,Kemaman,Kuala_Terengganu
E2	Balok_Baru,Kuala_Selangor,Manjung
E3	Kuala_Selangor,Seberang_Jaya,Perai,Manjung
E4	Seberang_Jaya,Perai
E5	PegohTaiping
E6	PegohTaipingTasek
E7	Alor_Setar,Balik_Pulau,Kangar,Langkawi
E8	Alor_Setar,Balik_Pulau,Kangar,Kulim,Langkawi,USM, Sungai_Petani
E9	Tanjung_Malim
E10	Nilai
E11	Indera Mahkota,Jerantut,Paka
E12	Batu_Muda,InderaMahkota,Jerantut,Paka,Pengerange, Port_Dickson,Segamat,Seremban,Kluang,Rompin,Temerloh
E13	Batu Pahat,Bukit_Rambai,Larkin,Pasir,Temerloh
E14	Cheras,Petaling_Jaya,Putrajaya,Shah_Alam
E15	Kota_Tinggi
E16	Banting

Appendix Table A6

Node ID	Stations Clustered
F1	Kulim,USM,Seberang_Jaya,Sungai_Petani,Perai
F2	Balik_Pulau,Minden,Pegoh,Taiping,Tasek
F3	Pegoh,Taiping
F4	Bandaraya_Melaka,Bukit_Rambai,Port_Dickson,Segamat
F5	Bukit_Rambai,Port_Dickson,Segamat,Seremban
F6	Kuala_Selangor,Manjung
F7	Batu Pahat,Cheras,Kuala_Selangor
F8	Batu Pahat
F9	InderaMahkota,Jerantut,Kemaman,Kota_Tinggi,Paka, Pengerange
F10	Rompin
F11	Balok_Baru
F12	Batu_Muda,Larkin,Pasir,Kluang,Temerloh
F13	Alor_Setar,Kangar,Langkawi,Tanjung_Malim
F14	Kuala_Terengganu
F15	Banting,Klang,Petaling_Jaya,Putrajaya,Shah_Alam
F16	Nilai

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- Madukpe, V. N., Zulkepli, N. F. S., Noorani, M. S. M., & Gobithaasan, R. U. (2025). Comparative analysis of Ball Mapper and conventional Mapper in investigating air pollutants' behavior. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 197(2). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-024-13477-2> (**SCIE-Indexed, Impact Factor 3.0**)
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- Zulkepli, N. F. S., Madukpe, V. N., Noorani, M. S. M., Bakar, M. A. A., Gobithaasan, R. U., & Jie, O. C. (2024). Topological clustering in investigating spatial patterns of particulate matter between air quality monitoring stations in Malaysia. *Air Quality, Atmosphere & Health*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11869-024-01596-1> (**SCIE-Indexed, Impact Factor 2.9**)
- Ishak, A.M., Zulkepli, N. F. S., Madukpe, V. N., Noorani, M. S. M., Gobithaasan, R. U. & Noorani, M. S. M. (2025). Topological Graph Representation of Haze Episodes Using the Mapper Algorithm with Multiple Distance Metrics. *AIP Conference Proceedings* [Accepted](**SCOPUS-Indexed**)